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TUMOR ABSORBED DOSE-RESPONSE RELATIONSHIPS IN TARGETED RADIONUCLIDE THERAPY

A PRECLINICAL INVESTIGATION OF LUTETIUM-177 AND
TERBIUM-161 RADIOLABELED PEPTIDES

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Preface

This thesis presents the doctoral research I carried out at the Belgian Nuclear Research Center (SCK CEN), in collaboration with KU Leuven, between October 2021 and September 2025. I am deeply grateful for the opportunity to start this research after completing my Master of Science in Physics. These years have allowed me to grow my knowledge and skills in medical physics, Monte Carlo simulations, and physical modeling. At the same time, the multidisciplinary nature of the project opened doors to new areas such as radiolabeling chemistry and *in vitro* and *in vivo* radiobiology, an exciting and enriching journey.

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On a more personal note, I thank my parents for giving me the chance to pursue higher education and for always encouraging me to follow my own interests. I am also deeply grateful to my boyfriend, Lander Meeuws, for his endless support and for making home a warm and comforting place after long days in the lab.

Finally, I thank you, the reader, for your interest in my work. I hope this thesis inspires you in some way and that it serves as a meaningful contribution to the field.

Summary

Targeted radionuclide therapy (TRT) employs radiopharmaceuticals that are designed to localize radioactive isotopes near cancerous cells. These radioisotopes undergo a nuclear decay and thereby emit radiation that interacts with the surrounding tissue and induces lethal damage. The most suitable radioisotopes are selected with ideally a short range radiation type for a more local irradiation, a half-life that matches biological half-life of the vector and a stable daughter radionuclide. The amount of energy the radiation deposits per mass of tissue is referred to as the absorbed dose in Gray (Gy), and is related to the amount of damage that is inflicted. However, absorbed dose calculations are rather complex in TRT since they require nuclear imaging at multiple time points, combined with physical dose deposition simulations, and are therefore often omitted.

The goal in TRT is to deliver a lethal radiation dose to the cancerous cells, while keeping the absorbed dose to healthy tissues below toxicity levels. However, due to the lack of standard applied dosimetry and longitudinal studies and limited radiobiological data, the absorbed dose-response relationships for both the tumor and healthy tissues are unknown for TRT. Consequently, all patients receive a fixed amount of injected activity for a fixed number of treatment cycles, despite inter-patient variations in kidney functioning, receptor expressions, tumor perfusion, tumor heterogeneity, body weight etc. Patients could largely benefit from more personalized treatments, either by safely increasing the absorbed dose to the tumor, or by reducing the absorbed dose to healthy tissues to avoid unnecessary toxicities. However, this would require both standard applied dosimetry as well as well established absorbed dose-response relationships, preferably including also a TRT-specific absorbed dose-response model, similar to the tumor control probability (TCP) models that are utilized during treatment planning in conventional external beam radiation therapy (EBRT).

Also at preclinical level, dosimetry is no standard practice yet. Nonetheless, preclinical absorbed dose-response relationships could reveal underlying radiobiological mechanisms, which remain undiscovered or show ambiguous results when considering only the administered activity. Furthermore, absorbed dose calculations would allow a more rigorous evaluation of new radiopharmaceuticals during their development. This brings us to the following aims for this PhD thesis:

- Investigating absorbed dose-response relationships for TRT, and thereby exploring the impact of TRT-specific irradiation characteristics, such as the low absorbed dose-rate, the heterogeneous absorbed dose distribution and the use of particle radiation instead of gamma radiation as used in conventional EBRT.
- Evaluating and comparing ^{161}Tb as a novel radioisotope for peptide receptor radionuclide therapy (PRRT) to ^{177}Lu , the standard radioisotope that is currently

used. Both isotopes are similar regarding their β^- -spectrum, half-life and chemical properties, while ^{161}Tb emits additional Auger and internal conversion (IC) electrons compared to ^{177}Lu , which could potentially increase the treatment efficacy.

In chapter 4, we established absorbed dose-response relationships *in vitro* for the clonogenic survival of CA20948 rat pancreatic cells after treatment with [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE, [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTA-LM3 and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3. These absorbed dose calculations were refined in chapter 5 by using more accurate S-values based on a more realistic, virtual CA20948 cell model instead of assuming a standard geometry of spherical cells. Complementary, in chapter 6, we investigated tumor absorbed dose-response relationships *in vivo* by performing a dose-escalating efficacy study using [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. Finally, chapter 6 linked together both the *in vitro* and *in vivo* absorbed dose-response relationships with an analytical tumor-growth-model, based on heterogeneous tumor absorbed dose distributions, determined from both *ex vivo* autoradiography and mouse-specific SPECT images.

In vitro absorbed dose-calculations have shown a 360 % higher absorbed dose to the cell nucleus for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE compared to [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE, while this was only a 30 % increase in absorbed dose at tumor level. This large difference was devoted to varying contributions of the short-range IC and long-range β^- electrons between the cellular and tumor level, which should be considered carefully when evaluating the potentials of [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. Moreover, it suggested a suitable application for the treatment of small metastases, for which the cross dose from the β^- electrons will be minimal, but the IC electrons from ^{161}Tb can still deliver a substantial absorbed dose.

Both at *in vitro* and *in vivo* level, we did not observe any difference in absorbed dose-response for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE compared to [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE. This could be explained by the range of the Auger electrons which was too short to reach the radiosensitive cell nucleus from within the cytoplasm, and thereby did not increase the biological effectiveness with their high linear energy transfer (LET). However, when the internalizing [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE was compared to the membrane bound [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 *in vitro*, we did observe an additional quadratic component in absorbed dose-response curve for the latter one, potentially due to additional cell membrane damage induced by the Auger electrons. However, this hypothesis requires further research, but indicates the importance of subcellular targeting when employing short-range radiation types such as Auger electrons.

Finally, we developed an analytical tumor-growth-model that was able to predict the tumor doubling time based on the cellular absorbed dose-response relationships. While the model largely overestimated the tumor doubling times when assuming a homogeneous absorbed dose distribution, the predictions improved substantially after a correction for the heterogeneous absorbed dose distributions, which illustrated the potential extensive impact of absorbed dose heterogeneity on TRT efficacy.

By performing accurate dosimetry both at *in vitro* and *in vivo* level, we were able to thoroughly investigate absorbed dose-response relationships within TRT. Our findings emphasized that absorbed dose heterogeneity, both at subcellular and tissue level, can have a profound effect on TRT efficacy. Furthermore, it allowed an in-depth comparison

of the currently used radioisotopes ^{161}Tb and ^{177}Lu for PRRT, and identified a larger potential of ^{161}Tb to treat small metastases, in addition to the importance of considering subcellular targeting when utilizing ^{161}Tb . Finally, we established and experimentally verified an analytical tumor-growth-model, which might bring us one step closer toward individualized treatments.

Acronyms

CF calibration factor

CT computed tomography

DPK dose point kernel

DSB double strand breaks

EANM European association of nuclear medicine

EBRT external beam radiation therapy

EMA European medicines agency

FDA food and drug administration

FOV field of view

GEP-NET gastroenteropancreatic neuroendocrine tumors

IC internal conversion

LAR long-acting repeatable

LET linear energy transfer

LQ linear-quadratic

MIRD medical internal radiation dosimetry

MPC metastatic control probability

MRI magnetic resonance imaging

NET neuroendocrine tumors

PDF probability density function

PET positron emission tomography

PFS progression-free survival

PRRT peptide receptor radionuclide therapy

PVE partial volume effect

RBE relative biological effectiveness

RC recovery coefficients

RP radiopharmaceuticals

SPECT single photon emission computed tomography

SSB single strand breaks

SSTR2 somatostatin receptor 2

TCP tumor control probability

TRT targeted radionuclide therapy

VCP voxel control probability

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Targeted radionuclide therapy (TRT) offers a novel treatment option for patients with non-resectable or metastasized tumors, who could benefit from a systemic therapy other than chemo-, hormone or immunotherapy. Well-selected radioisotopes, that emit locally damaging radiation, are linked to a targeting vector and are as such specifically directed to the cancer cells. Moreover, co-emitted gamma-photons allow to image the tumor and healthy tissue uptake, thereby enabling monitoring of the treatment response and healthy tissue toxicities at each intermediate cycle. In addition, a diagnostic agent that binds to the same target, optimized for imaging and quantification, can be combined for patient selection. This principle is referred to as '(radio-)theranostics' and enables individualized treatments.

However, in practice, unlike in conventional external beam radiation therapy (EBRT), individualized treatments in TRT are still far from standard. While in EBRT each patient receives a personalized treatment plan in order to attain the therapeutic window (*i.e.* maximize the absorbed dose to the tumor tissue, while maintaining healthy tissue absorbed doses below the prescribed limits), in TRT each patient receives a standard number of treatment cycles, where for each cycle, a fixed amount of activity is administered. Although this one-fits-all approach has proven to be safe and effective, it ignores patient-specific variations in tumor load, receptor expression levels, tumor perfusion, bio-kinetics, kidney functioning etc. which might result in under-treating patients. However, prerequisites to safely adapt the treatment plan for each patient individually are both standardized dosimetry and well-established absorbed dose-response relationships, which are not available for TRT to date. This emphasizes the need to include dosimetry in clinical, but also preclinical, TRT research, to be able to correlate observed tumor responses and organ toxicities with absorbed dose, thereby allowing proper radiobiological evaluations of therapy efficacy and finding the most optimal balance between safety and effectiveness for every patient.

1.1 Dosimetry in TRT

The absence of standard applied dosimetry in TRT is partially devoted to its complexity. The principle of medical internal radiation dosimetry (MIRD) calculates the absorbed dose to a target region r_T as a sum of contributions of all potential source regions r_S

that irradiate the target region r_T during an irradiation time T_D :

$$D(r_T, T_D) = \sum_{r_S} \tilde{A}(r_S, T_D) S(r_T \leftarrow r_S) \quad (1.1)$$

(1). The time-integrated-activity, or cumulated activity, $\tilde{A}(r_S, T_D)$ represents the number of nuclear disintegrations within the source region r_S over time T_D after administration of a radiopharmaceutical. This factor is multiplied with the isotope- and geometry-specific S-value, defined as the contribution of a source region r_S to the absorbed dose delivered to the target region r_T , per nuclear disintegration in that source region. Despite the well-defined formalism, absorbed dose estimates can result in large uncertainties since the simulation of S-values involves assumptions about geometry, including the size of the different source and target regions and their relative locations. In addition, the time-integrated activity coefficients are often extracted from only a limited number of nuclear medicine images, which are in addition prone to errors induced by the limited resolution and related partial volume effects, noise effects, segmentation uncertainties and traceability of activity quantification.

Also at preclinical level, dosimetry for TRT has its specific challenges. Although small animal studies can rely on *in vivo* nuclear medical imaging with systems that are specifically designed and optimized for small animal imaging, these preclinical images also suffer from similar issues as the clinical images that are used for dosimetry. On the other hand, additional methods such as *ex vivo* gamma counting and autoradiography are also available. These approaches allow to determine the absorbed dose more accurately and the relative absorbed dose distribution at a higher resolution, respectively, although they are both inherently population averaged. As opposed to this, *in vitro* cellular dosimetry is in no way similar to clinical dosimetry. The time-activity curve is determined from saturation binding, association, dissociation and internalization studies, and the contribution from surrounding cells is minimal, thereby increasing the importance of detailed cellular modeling to determine the self-dose. More details on preclinical dosimetry can be found in a published review paper 'A Review on Tumor Control Probability and Preclinical Dosimetry in Targeted Radionuclide Therapy' that can be found in chapter 2 (2).

1.1.1 Nuclear Medicine Imaging

Nuclear medicine imaging has been used extensively for various diagnostic applications, by the use of either a planar gamma camera, single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) or positron emission tomography (PET). These functional images are usually combined with anatomical images from a computed tomography (CT) scan or a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scan, to localize the 3D distribution of a radiotracer in the patient. In a SPECT scan, isotropic gamma photon emissions are limited to specific directions, by the use of a collimator, prior to their detection at multiple angles around the patient. The acquired projections are then used to compute a 3D reconstruction of the activity distribution. A PET scan does not require a collimator, since it detects the 511 keV gamma photons following positron annihilation, which are emitted in opposite directions, and thereby already define the direction of emission, which allows to compute a 3D reconstruction. The latter one results in an improved resolution and sensitivity, but requires the use of a surrogate radionuclide, while a SPECT scan can in many cases directly image the

therapeutic radionuclide and thus the delivered therapy.

Some therapeutic radioisotopes co-emit gamma photons that are suitable for detection with a SPECT camera, such as ^{177}Lu or ^{161}Tb (Tab. 1.1), which allows to verify the therapeutic radiopharmaceutical distribution. However, these gamma photons are often at lower intensities and have sub-optimal energies, resulting in more noisy data with reduced image quality. Therefore, a more optimal surrogate radioisotope is often used for patient selection and post-treatment evaluation, which is referred to as a theranostic pair, such as ^{68}Ga -DOTATATE and ^{177}Lu -DOTATATE for example (3). Moreover, theranostic imaging demands a quantitative image instead of a relative activity distribution to be able to perform absorbed dose calculations.

Table 1.1: The decay properties of the isotopes ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb , taken from ICRP107 (4).

	^{177}Lu	^{161}Tb
Half-life	6.644 d	6.953 d
γ -photons for imaging	113 keV (6 %) 208 keV (10 %)	48.9 keV (17 %) 74.6 keV (10 %)
β^- energy / decay	134 keV	156 keV
# IC e^- / decay	0.15	1.4
IC energy / decay	13 keV	39 keV
# Auger e^- / decay	1.1	11
Auger energy / decay	1.1 keV	8.9 keV

Quantitative nuclear medicine imaging involves the use of a calibration factor (CF) to convert the reconstructed count rates into activity concentrations. These are determined by either large phantoms or point sources with known activity concentrations traceable to reference activities measured in a radionuclide calibrator, thereby already introducing a first source of uncertainty and inter-center variability. Next to the CF, also recovery coefficients (RC) can be considered to account for the partial volume effect (PVE) and avoid the underestimation of activity in small volumes due to the limited resolution. PVE can induce large variations, leading up to 118 % quantification differences between different systems for spheres with diameters ≤ 25 mm in clinical ^{177}Lu SPECT images (5). The reconstruction algorithm has also an impact on the quantification and should incorporate corrections for photon attenuation and Compton scatter (6), in addition to a model for the collimator response to reduce the variation in resolution across the field of view (FOV). Furthermore, should be segmented either fully manually or (semi-)automatically on the SPECT images with guidance from the co-registered CT images. Finally a time-activity curve should be established, which requires activity sampling at multiple time points, preferably up to two times the effective half-life (*i.e.* ~ 100 h for ^{177}Lu -DOTATATE kidney dosimetry) to avoid inter- or extrapolation errors (7).

1.1.2 Monte Carlo Simulations

Once the activity distribution is known, it should be multiplied with the appropriate S-value that specifies where the emitted radiation deposits its energy. This strongly depends on the energy, range and density of the electrons as well as on the geometry of the lesions and organs of interest. Monte Carlo particle transportation codes, such as Geant4 and its derivative GATE, are able to simulate the interaction of the emitted

particles with the surrounding tissue materials, and thereby can evaluate the absorbed dose distribution. Due to its computational burden, it has only gained momentum in the last decades, with the availability of increased computational power. Monte Carlo simulations have the advantage of being versatile and being able to handle complex geometries with multiple tissue interfaces, however, in practice, simplified methods are used. User-friendly software, such as OLINDA and IDAC-dose, for example, are able to calculate absorbed doses using predefined S-values for standardized geometries of models representing an adult male and female among others.

1.2 Absorbed Dose-Response in TRT

The physical absorbed dose quantifies the energy deposition of radiation per tissue mass and is therefore one of the driving factors for tumor and healthy tissue response to radiation exposure. In EBRT, the relation between the absorbed dose and the probability of clonogenic cell survival S is in general described by the linear-quadratic model:

$$S(D) = e^{-\alpha \cdot D - \beta \cdot D^2}. \quad (1.2)$$

This empirically derived relation is interpreted as follows: the linear component α represents the damage from single radiation tracks causing lethal DNA damage by double strand breaks (DSB) and the quadratic component β represents the damage from two separate radiation tracks each producing sublethal single strand breaks (SSB), which interact to induce lethal cell damage. This model allows to estimate the TCP based on the absorbed dose D via

$$TCP = (1 - S(D))^{n_0}, \quad (1.3)$$

with n_0 the number of clonogenic cells. Such a TCP model is of large value when optimizing the treatment plan, however, a direct translation towards TRT is possible, but requires some adaptations due to inherent differences between both treatment modalities. While EBRT utilizes gamma irradiation, homogeneously delivered within a few minutes at a high dose-rate (~ 1 Gy / min), TRT delivers a heterogeneous dose distribution – both at tissue and (sub)cellular level – over a few days time at a low dose-rate (~ 1 Gy / h) by the emission of electron (β^- , IC, Auger) or alpha radiation. The low dose-rate allows extensive repair of sub-lethal DNA damages and thereby reduces the contribution of sub-lethal damages β , while the difference in radiation type (photons vs electrons) can alter the intrinsic radiosensitivity α . The use of short-range radiation types in TRT will generate a heterogeneous absorbed dose distribution at the subcellular level corresponding to specific subcellular pathways of the radiopharmaceutical, and this heterogeneous absorbed dose distribution usually does not match with the radiosensitive cell compartments, such as the DNA within the cell nucleus, thereby reducing the overall treatment efficacy. Moreover, also at tissue level, variations in receptor expression and perfusion will generate a heterogeneous absorbed dose distribution, thereby generating a wide spread in absorbed dose per cell, and consequently reducing the overall TCP, since this is largely determined by the lowest absorbed dose regions. Therefore, TRT demands for a more appropriate dose-response model, that can represent more clinically relevant outcomes, such as progression-free survival (PFS), instead of TCP. More details on how each of these aspects could be incorporated in a TRT-specific dose-response model are presented in detail in a previously published review paper, that can be found in chapter 2.

Next to a proper analytical model describing absorbed dose-response relations in TRT, also related experimental data are only sparsely available for TRT. Only recently, some clinical trials did report a positive correlation between the lesion absorbed doses and response, expressed as delay in PFS (8–11). This correlation was lacking in another study which could be attributed to limitations in the imaging methods that complicated the assessment of the lesion size, namely the use of planar scintigraphy and the absence of a correction for PVE (12), but again highlights the difficulties in establishing dose-response relationships. The radiobiology working group of the European association of nuclear medicine (EANM), analyzed prior literature on dose-response relationships for neuroendocrine tumors (NET) to [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE¹ treatment and identified three zones (13). In zone 1, the ‘unpredictable response zone’, it would be impossible to predict the tumor response based on the absorbed dose. Above a threshold absorbed dose around 90 - 100 Gy (8), 110 - 125 Gy (11) or 120 Gy (10), in zone 2, the ‘effective response zone’, all lesions would show a stable disease (< 20 % tumor growth based on RECIST criteria, note that this would still yield a TCP = 0). At even higher absorbed doses (>> 175 Gy (8), arbitrary threshold), the tumor response might reach a plateau, which defines zone 3, the ‘unnecessary absorbed dose zone’. However, these thresholds are based on limited available data, which moreover show large variations between the different studies. Therefore, more research based on clinical trial data is needed to better understand the absorbed dose-response relationships for TRT, which are required to allow personalized treatment strategies.

1.3 ¹⁷⁷Lu and ¹⁶¹Tb-Labelled Radiopeptides for NETs

The majority of the absorbed dose-response data that is currently available for TRT focuses on [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE treatment of gastroenteropancreatic neuroendocrine tumors (GEP-NET). This radiopeptide combines the β^- -emitting isotope Lutetium-177 with the somatostatin-analogue octreotide, that binds specifically to the somatostatin receptor 2 (SSTR2) which is overexpressed on the cell surface of NETs. Both the NETTER-1 and NETTER-2 phase 3 clinical trials showed a significantly ($p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.0001$, respectively) longer progression-free survival of [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE treatment compared to the standard high-dose octreotide long-acting repeatable (LAR) treatment, with limited acute toxic effects, which had led to its approval by both the European medicines agency (EMA)(2017) and the U.S. food and drug administration (FDA)(2018) (14, 15). However, alternative radiopeptides might still outperform [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE, since the final analysis of the NETTER-1 trial was not able to show any significantly increase in median overall survival (16).

One alternative is the use of SSTR2 antagonists, such as DOTA-LM3². They remain membrane-bound, as opposed to the agonist DOTATATE that internalizes into the cell. First results with ¹⁷⁷Lu-labeled antagonists showed an increase in the kidney, bone-marrow as well as tumor uptake and retention, with an overall increase in both the tumor-to-kidney and tumor-to-bone-marrow ratio (17–19). At the same time, unlike the agonists, antagonists did not show tumor saturation yet up to 2 nmol, which was in favor of the tumor-to-liver and tumor-to-bone-marrow ratio and suggested a lower affinity (20). However, despite the increased tumor-to-healthy tissue ratios,

¹DOTA-Tyr3-octreotate

²DOTA-[p-CI-Phe-cyclo(D-Cys-Tyr-D-4-amino-Phe(carbamoyl)-Lys-Thr-Cys)D-Tyr-NH2]

increased hematological toxicity was observed for antagonists compared to agonist at similar bone marrow absorbed doses, potentially due to the increased binding to hematopoietic stem cells and multipotent progenitor cells (21, 22). Furthermore, their membrane localization was identified to be beneficial when combined with short-range radiation types (23). Further research, accompanied with accurate dosimetry, is needed to better understand the benefits of the use of antagonists compared to agonists.

Also the choice of the radioisotope is under investigation. The more local irradiation of [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE resulted in reduced hematological and renal toxicity compared to its predecessor [^{90}Y]Y-DOTATATE, which utilized the long-range β^- -emitter Yttrium-90 (mean β^- range: 0.26 mm for ^{177}Lu vs. 4 mm for ^{90}Y (24)) (25). Next to this already improved toxicity profile, the irradiation characteristics of other isotopes might be even more favorable. The isotope Terbium-161 emits more short-range low-energy Auger and IC electrons compared to ^{177}Lu , while it emits a similar β^- -spectrum with an almost identical half-life and similar chemical properties (Tab.1.1, Fig. 1.1). The metastatic prostate cancer model of Bernhardt et al. showed that the emission of additional low-energy electrons by ^{161}Tb are especially beneficial for small metastasis ($< 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3$), for which the absorbed dose from ^{177}Lu would be insufficient due to a substantial spill-out of the emitted β^- electrons out of the lesion volume. (26). Moreover, the low-energy Auger electrons are characterized by an increased LET, which might potentially increase the biological effectiveness and thus the absorbed dose-response, since in EBRT the use of higher LET particle radiation has been shown to increase the relative biological effectiveness (RBE) significantly (27). Some preclinical studies have already shown an increased tumor response for ^{161}Tb -labeled peptides compared to ^{177}Lu -labeled analogues, when administering the same activities (23). However, an accurate absorbed dose-response comparison is still lacking.

Figure 1.1: The emission spectra of the β^- , IC and Auger electrons for ^{161}Tb and ^{177}Lu from ICRP107 database (4). Note the different energy scales.

Chapter 2

A Review on Tumor Control Probability and Preclinical Dosimetry in Targeted Radionuclide Therapy

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Abstract

Targeted Radionuclide Therapy (TRT) uses radiopharmaceuticals to specifically irradiate tumor cells while sparing healthy tissue. Response to this treatment highly depends on the absorbed dose. Tumor control probability (TCP) models aim to predict the tumor response based on the absorbed dose by taking into account the different characteristics of TRT. For instance, TRT employs radiation with a high linear energy transfer (LET), which results in an increased effectiveness. Furthermore, a heterogeneous radiopharmaceutical distribution could result in a heterogeneous dose distribution at a tissue, cellular as well as subcellular level, which will generally reduce the tumor response. Finally, the dose rate in TRT is protracted, relatively low and variable over time. This allows cells to repair more DNA damage which may reduce the effectiveness of TRT. Within this review an overview is given on how these characteristics can be included in TCP models, while also some experimental findings are discussed. Many parameters in TCP models are preclinically determined and TCP models also play a role in the preclinical stage of radiopharmaceutical development, however, this all depends critically on the calculated absorbed dose. Accordingly, an overview of the existing preclinical dosimetry methods is given, together with their limitation and applications. It can be concluded that although the theoretical extension of TCP models from external beam radiotherapy towards TRT has been established quite well, the experimental confirmation is lacking. This asks for additional comprehensive studies at the sub-cellular, cellular and organ level,

which should be provided with accurate preclinical dosimetry.

2.1 Introduction

Ever since the discovery of ionizing radiation at the end of the 19th century, it has been exploited for various medical applications. One of them is cancer treatments, where the aim is to deliver a high absorbed dose to the tumor, while minimizing the radiation burden to healthy tissue. Targeted radionuclide therapy (TRT) is a relatively novel approach where a radionuclide can be coupled to well-designed vectors who specifically target the cancerous cells. These so-called radiopharmaceuticals (RP) are administered systemically and thus are able to target cancerous cells throughout the whole body such that inoperable or metastasized tumors can be treated.

The emission of short-range alpha, beta or Auger electron radiation by specific radionuclides causes DNA damage within the cancerous cells, thereby inducing cell death by a very localized dose deposition. Although approved radiopharmaceutical treatment schedules usually follow the 'one size fits all' approach, each patient may display a different treatment response based on tumor volume, radiosensitivity of tumor cells, biokinetics of the RP and the repair mechanisms of tumor cells. Individualized treatment planning is currently not yet standard practice of care in TRT, but may significantly improve therapeutic efficacy. Personalized treatment would benefit from a mathematical model that is able to predict the treatment outcome for a specific patient and a given absorbed dose. From external beam radiotherapy (EBRT), there is the Tumor Control Probability (TCP) model with $TCP = 0$ corresponding to no response expected, while $TCP = 1$ corresponds to a 100% chance that all cancerous cells will be killed and the patient is cured. The general TCP model accounts for the overall absorbed dose and the radiosensitivity of tumor tissue while it makes a distinction between repairable, sub-lethal DNA single strand breaks (SSB) and unreparable, lethal DNA double strand breaks (DSB), as will be explained in section 2.2. More extensive models also incorporate the effects of tumor repopulation, tumor heterogeneity, differences in dose rate and linear energy transfer (LET), and heterogeneous dose distributions, of which the latter three are especially relevant in TRT.

For EBRT, an abundance of data has been collected over the past decades, which resulted in well-established TCP models (28). A direct translation to the more novel TRT is however not straightforward since their irradiation characteristics differ substantially. Unlike EBRT, TRT results in an absorbed dose that is heterogeneously distributed across the tumor both on a tissue and subcellular level while the dose rate is protracted, relatively low and variable over time. Furthermore, TRT exploits high and medium LET alpha, beta or Auger electron radiation while in EBRT low LET X-rays are used. These fundamental differences alter the tumor response and should be incorporated in TRT-specific TCP models. Section 2.3 describes these differences more in detail, while section 2.4 incorporates proliferation and tumor heterogeneity into the TCP model, which are two important radiobiological aspects in both TRT and EBRT.

Next to the clinical relevance of TCP models, their preclinical importance is also highlighted. In the framework of RP development for example, TCP models can

evaluate different combinations of radionuclides and vectors to select the most promising candidates for clinical translation. However, a prerequisite for the correct use of TCP models in preclinical settings is accurate dosimetry. This review discusses the use of dosimetry in preclinical research, with the conclusion that often major assumptions are made or dosimetry is even completely omitted. Nonetheless, Konijnenberg *et al.* showed the critical dependence of TCP on the dose (29) such that even small variations in absorbed tumor dose can alter the TCP substantially. This means that inaccurate dose estimates can lead to ambiguous results or incorrect dose-response relationships.

2.2 TCP Modelling

Since radiation-induced cell death is a stochastic process, TCP models are essentially statistical models. A commonly used TCP model utilizes the Poisson distribution $P(n)$ to describe the probability for n out of n_0 clonogenic cells to survive a treatment (30). TCP then corresponds to the chance that none of them survives,

$$TCP = P(n = 0) = e^{-n_0 S}, \quad (2.1)$$

where S is the chance for a single cell to survive. Next to the Poisson distribution, the Binomial distribution $B(n)$ —which can be regarded as the discrete version of the continuous Poisson distribution—can also be used to describe TCP :

$$TCP = B(n = 0) = (1 - S)^{n_0} \quad (2.2)$$

(31). Both of these models coincide for a large number of clonogenic cells n_0 and a small cell survival probability S , which is the case for typical radiation treatments ($n_0 \approx 10^9$ for 1 cm³ tumor tissue and $S \approx 10^{-1}$ for 2 Gy) (31, 32).

The next step is to find an expression for the probability of a single cell to survive the treatment, *i.e.* S from equations 2.1 and 2.2. A widely accepted cell survival model is the linear quadratic model (LQ) (see figure 2.1), for which the strength is to be experimentally confirmed while providing radiobiological insights (33). The basic LQ model is stated as

$$S = e^{-\alpha D - \beta G D^2}. \quad (2.3)$$

The exponent consists of a linear and a quadratic term with each term representing a distinct type of lethal DNA damage that can induce cell death. As described in detail by Dale *et al.*, lethal DNA damage can either originate from a single ionizing event or from multiple individual sub-lethal ionizing events (34, 35). The latter one requires at least two proximal, independent ionizing interactions to induce lethal cell damage, which results in a quadratic dependence on the dose D .

The contribution of the linear part is determined by the radiosensitivity parameter α . It depends on the irradiated tissue characteristics (oxygenation, cell cycle phase, etc.) as well as on the linear energy transfer (LET) of the radiation. LET is defined as the amount of energy that is deposited per unit distance and thus quantifies the density of the ionisation tracks for a particular type of radiation. High LET radiation is marked by dense ionisation tracks, which will induce more DNA damages. Note that a single radiation event will result in mainly lethal damages, such that high LET radiation will show an increased linear component α . Examples of high LET radiations are

Figure 2.1: Cell survival and tumor control probability (TCP) curves of external beam radiotherapy (EBRT) vs. targeted radionuclide therapy (TRT), including the comparison between alpha and beta radiation (left panel) as well as homogeneous vs. heterogeneous dose (right panel, for beta radiation). While EBRT has a linear-quadratic survival curve, the one of TRT is more linear. Alpha particles are more effective compared to EBRT, while beta particles are less effective. The TCP curves show that the heterogeneous dose distributions decreases the efficacy. Most of the input data is taken from Bernhardt *et al.* who simulated a metastatic control probability model for prostate cancer (26) ($T_{eff} = 51$ h, $T_r = 1.9$ h, $\alpha/\beta = 1.5$ Gy, $\alpha = 0.147$ Gy $^{-1}$ and $N = 1.79 \cdot 10^8$), combined with the relative biological effectiveness (RBE) values of 1.5 and 14 for ^{177}Lu and ^{241}Am respectively for the prostate cancer cell line PC3 (36). For the dose heterogeneity, a lognormal dose distribution with shape parameter $\sigma_D = 0.1$ was assumed.

alpha particles and Auger electrons. Beta particles and X-rays on the other hand are categorised as low LET radiation and are thus less damaging.

The quadratic part consists of the β constant together with the Lea-Catcheside or dose-protraction factor G . The latter one, G , adjusts the quadratic part for the ability of cells to repair sub-lethal damage prior to a second ionization event which is needed to cause lethal damage. This depends on the time scale of the repair mechanisms on the one hand and the dose rate on the other hand. For an arbitrary dose rate \dot{D} and repair function $f_r(t)$ rate μ , the Lea-Catcheside factor is defined as

$$G(\dot{D}, \mu) = \frac{2}{D^2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \dot{D}(t) dt \int_{-\infty}^t \dot{D}(t') f_r(t' - t) dt' \quad (2.4)$$

with $f_r(t) = e^{-\mu t}$ with repair rate μ for a single compartment repair function (30). Finally, this factor is multiplied by the constant β , which indicates how sensitive a particular type of tissue is to changes in dose rate or irradiation schemes (34). However, the ratio α/β is mostly reported, which is high for fast responding tissues, such as tumor tissue, and low for late responding tissues.

The radiobiological constants α and β can be accessed by a fitting of equation 2.3 to survival curves, which can be provided by *in vitro* colony survival assays. Herein the ability of a single cell to grow into a colony is evaluated as function of the

absorbed dose. The resulting parameters depend largely on the dosimetry which is used to determine the absorbed dose. This is described in detail in section 2.5.2. The repair constant μ is required to calculate the Lea-Catcheside factor. This is commonly achieved by looking at the amount of DNA damage over time via γ -H2AX assays, which is complicated for TRT due to protracted DNA damage induction and thus would require differential equations describing DNA damage induction, repair and cell growth. Forand *et al.* have shown that after DNA repair, γ -H2AX remains temporarily localised near the initial DNA damage, which should be taken into account (37).

The TCP model can be extended in case of metastatic disease. Herein, multiple tumors of varying size are present and the metastatic control probability (MCP) represents the chance that all m metastases are cured:

$$MCP = \prod_{i=1}^m TCP_i \quad (2.5)$$

(26).

2.3 TCP for Targeted Radionuclide Therapy

Radionuclide therapy is characterized by (i) a relatively low dose rate on a protracted timescale that varies over time, (ii) a heterogeneous dose distribution on different levels and (iii) radiation with various LET such as high LET alpha particles or Auger electrons and low LET electron radiation, in contrast with EBRT, which uses only low LET X-rays. To what extent these characteristics will affect the TCP depends on the radiation type. Alpha particles and Auger electrons have a very short-range compared to beta particles (see table 2.1), such that the effect of dose heterogeneity will be much more pronounced. Furthermore, the high LET of the alpha particles and Auger electrons results in mainly lethal DNA damage. Accordingly, the effect of dose rate on the repair of sub-lethal damages will be minimal for high LET radiation, while this is an important factor for low LET beta particles. The following sections will discuss these effects in detail.

Table 2.1: Overview of the radiation types used in targeted radionuclide therapy. For each radiation type, a specific example is given together with the energy, the range and the linear energy transfer (LET) of the emitted particles (38).

Radionuclide	Radiation type	Energy	Range	LET
^{90}Y	beta	50-2300 keV	0.05-12 mm	0.2 keV/mm
^{111}In	Auger	eV-keV	2-500 nm	4-6 keV/mm
^{225}Ac	alpha	5-9 MeV	40-100 μm	80 keV/mm

2.3.1 Dose Rate

The dose rate within the tumor is relatively low in TRT compared to EBRT. Furthermore, the dose rate changes over time with an initial increase during the uptake phase of the RP, followed by a slow exponential decrease, determined by both the physical decay and the biological half life of the RP. The low dose rate allows cells

to repair the majority of the sub-lethal DNA damage prior to a secondary ionization event. This leads to a reduced dose-response effect. On the other hand, when both tumor and healthy tissues receive a similar dose rate, this may lead to a healthy tissue sparing effect (35). As mentioned before, since high LET radiation induces mainly lethal damages, this effect will be most important for low LET radiation such as beta particles.

Note that the Lea-Catcheside factor describes exactly this phenomenon. Its definition—equation (2.4)—requires the dose rate scheme and the repair rate as input. Solanki *et al.* derived an expression of G for TRT which includes both the uptake and excretion phase (39). However, the assumption that the RP is taken up immediately, substantially simplifies the result:

$$G_{TRT} \approx \frac{\lambda_{eff}}{\mu + \lambda_{eff}}. \quad (2.6)$$

μ is the repair rate and λ_{eff} is the effective decay constant of the RP. When DNA repair is fast compared to the dose rate ($\mu \gg \lambda_{eff}$) then $G_{TRT} \approx 0$ such that the contribution of the quadratic part, depicting lethal damage by superimposed ionization events, will be minimal. The cell survival curve will therefore be more linear as is shown in figure 2.1. Including the gradual, initial uptake phase of the RP will reduce the Lea-Catcheside factor G even further. Moreover, Solanki *et al.* found *in vitro* that a longer uptake phase could even reduce the efficacy during the clearance phase, which might be the result of adaptive tumor responses (39).

Recently, Gholami *et al.* investigated the effect of dose rate *in vitro* by comparing both low and high dose rate ^{90}Y TRT with EBRT (40). They reported a tremendous reduction of the contribution of the quadratic part for reduced dose rates as well as an overall reduced efficacy as expected. The other way around, Nonnekens *et al.* were able to block the repair of single cell breaks in the DNA using a PARP inhibitor and observed a significant reduction in cell survival (41). Unfortunately, no dose was reported and hence no α , β and G values could be estimated.

A final remark on dose rate is that at extremely low dose rates, the eradication of clonogenic cells might be in competition with cell proliferation. The critical dose rate at which cell eradication matches cell proliferation, is expressed via

$$R_{crit} = \frac{\ln 2}{\alpha T_p},$$

where T_p is the cell proliferation doubling time and α the cell radiosensitivity (42). At a certain time, the dose rate during TRT will drop below this critical value such that tumor cell proliferation will exceed cell death.

2.3.2 Heterogeneous Dose Distribution

Following administration to the patient, radiopharmaceuticals are distributed throughout the tumor and deliver a dose to the surrounding tumor tissue up to a maximum range, which is specific for each radionuclide. Accordingly, the non-homogeneous distribution of a RP within the tumor can be translated into a non-homogeneous dose distribution (see figure 2.2). At tissue level, this can be

observed as an inter-cellular dose heterogeneity. Each cell receives a different dose, and consequently shows a distinct treatment response. At cellular level, the subcellular pathway of the RP results in an intra-cellular dose heterogeneity as well. Internalisation will increase the dose to the cell nucleus for particles with a short range, and since the nucleus is considered as the primary target, this is expected to increase the TCP.

Figure 2.2: Immunofluorescent staining of receptor expression (somatostatin receptor 2) on a tumor tissue section, showing a heterogeneous receptor expression (left) and corresponding heterogeneous dose distribution in Gray for the β^- -emitter ^{177}Lu (right) (43).

2.3.2.1 Tumor/Tissue Dose Heterogeneity

On a tissue level, radiopharmaceuticals may be heterogeneously distributed due to a heterogeneous receptor expression and differences in perfusion, where limited perfusion can prevent radiopharmaceuticals of reaching the tumor cells. This results in a heterogeneous dose distribution as well, for which the low and high dose regions can differ by a factor 5 as was observed by Timmermand *et al.* (44). A heterogeneous dose distribution induces a correlated nonuniform treatment response (45, 46). In order to account for heterogeneity in the TCP model, multiple compartments can be defined, such that the dose D_i in each compartment can be considered homogeneous. At tissue level such a compartment can be a voxel (*i.e.* 3D pixel), originating from 3D *in vivo* imaging techniques or autoradiography images (see section 2.5.3), while for *in vitro* studies the compartments could refer to single cells. Consequently, a voxel control probability (VCP) can be assigned to each compartment, representing the probability that this specific compartment will be controlled. The overall TCP is then the probability that all the compartments are controlled:

$$TCP = \prod_i VCP(D_i). \quad (2.7)$$

This concept was first used by A.E. Nahum to investigate the effect of a reduced dose at the tumor boundary (47). More recently this concept was extended by Uusijärvi *et al.* (48) who employed hypothetical normal and log-normal activity distributions over the tumor tissue. Both *in silico* studies found a reduced TCP for a heterogeneous dose distribution compared to an analogue homogeneous distribution, as expected. Repopulation occurs within tumor regions receiving a low dose which in turn reduces the treatment efficacy. Increased dose barely affects regions with (almost) no radionuclide uptake and hence show a saturation in the cell survival curve (49). In contrast, Tamborino *et al.* predicted an increased efficacy for a heterogeneous dose distribution based on autoradiography images of *in vivo* tumor models (43). They

devote this observation to the use of a cell-line with a more homogeneous receptor expression in combination with the beta particle-emitting radionuclide (^{177}Lu), which most likely blurred the effect. This contradiction indicates that more experimental data is required to investigate the effect of a heterogeneous dose distribution on the treatment outcome.

The dose heterogeneity issue could theoretically be overcome by the use of radionuclides with a longer range. This way, regions with low RP uptake could still be irradiated by the so called cross-fire effect of radionuclides further away. However, long-range radiation is less suitable for smaller tumors or metastases since a great fraction of the energy is deposited outside of the tumor (50). Furthermore, long-range beta electrons are also observed to be less effective compared to short-range Auger electrons and alpha particles due to the difference in LET (51, 52). The metastatic tumor model of Bernhardt *et al.* shows nicely how each radionuclide has their own optimal tumor volume (26). Therefore the optimal radionuclide needs to be selected depending on the tumor size. For metastatic disease, one could utilize a mix of radionuclides to combine the advantages of different types of radiation (53, 54).

2.3.2.2 Subcellular Dose Heterogeneity

Alpha particles and Auger electrons have an extremely short-range of 28 – 100 μm and several nanometers, respectively (55). Consequently, their subcellular pathway results in an intra-cellular dose heterogeneity. As such, TCP can substantially increase when the absorbed dose to radiosensitive cell organelles is maximized. The nuclear DNA is considered the primary target since non-repairable DNA damage can result in apoptosis and indeed, many studies have shown a clear nuclear dose-response relationship, as summarised by Bavelaar *et al.* (56). RP may be directed towards the nucleus via receptor-mediated internalization, or targeting of endosomes, which even increases the efficacy for longer-range radiation such as ^{177}Lu (57). Furthermore, differential internalisation between the tumor and healthy cells might therefore increase the therapeutic index.

The previous paragraph applies for alpha particles and beta particles with a short range. However, the range of Auger electrons is too small to target the nuclear DNA from inside the cytoplasm. Nonetheless, Auger-emitting particles have shown to be effective from inside the cytoplasm. A study by Feudenberg *et al.* clearly suggested the existence of extra-nuclear targets for Auger electrons (58) such as the mitochondria and cell membrane. Damage to these targets may induce cell death, though with less sensitivity (56). Recent findings even suggest that Auger emitters coupled to cell membrane-targeting antagonists might be more potent than internalising or nuclear targeting agonists (23). However, these findings could also be the result of the overall higher tumor uptake of the antagonists. Therefore, absorbed doses to the main cell compartments and/or organelles (nucleus, cytoplasm, cell membrane) need to be estimated accurately before any conclusion can be drawn from these results.

2.3.3 Linear Energy Transfer

The third aspect for modelling response in TRT is the radiation quality. In EBRT, the dose is delivered via X-ray photons while TRT exploits the short-range alpha and beta

radiation as well as Auger and Conversion electrons. Besides the specific range of each radiation type, they also distinct themselves by means of their LET. As explained in section 2.2, the more effective DNA damage induced by higher LET radiation results in an increase of the contribution of the linear α component. This can be observed by the more steep and straight survival curve for higher LET radiation (30).

The relative biological effectiveness (RBE) quantifies this effect by evaluating the dose from the investigated high LET radiation D that is required to obtain the same biological endpoint (*e.g.* cell survival) as a dose D_{ref} from a reference low LET radiation:

$$RBE = \frac{D_{ref}}{D}. \quad (2.8)$$

However, this is a variable quantity as it depends on the selected reference dose, the biological endpoint and on the α/β ratio of the tissue (59). Claesson *et al.* showed that the RBE is also affected by the cell cycle phase and reported an RBE variation between 1.8 up to 8.6 (60). In order to exclude the dependence on the reference dose, Dale and Jones introduced the intrinsic RBE_m , which is defined as the RBE at zero dose, such that it reflects the ratio of the initial slopes of the survival curves and thus the ratio of the α -components of the LQ model (59). This concept can be used to include the radiation quality in the TCP model via

$$\alpha = \alpha_{ref} \cdot RBE_m, \quad (2.9)$$

where α_{ref} is the radiosensitivity for the reference radiation, which only depends on the tissue.

It should be noted that experimentally evaluating the RBE is not an obvious task. The cell survival curves for each radiation type as well as the reference radiation requires highly accurate dosimetry in order to extract the α and β values. In section 2.5.2, 28 reported survival curves in function of dose for TRT are evaluated. For those who compared the response of TRT to EBRT, the RBE_m was calculated via equation 2.9 and reported in table 2.2. Unfortunately, large variations in RBE were observed, which results in substantial standard deviations and thus meaningless results. Therefore, these values need to be interpreted with care.

2.4 Extended Modelling

The previous section focused on the specific characteristics of radionuclide therapy, such as dose rate, dose heterogeneity and LET. However, radiobiological characteristics that are relevant to radiation therapy in general, can be implemented into a TCP model as well. Three important aspects are tumor proliferation or repopulation, tumor heterogeneity and bystander effects.

2.4.1 Repopulation

During the treatment, the irradiated tumor will ideally start to shrink because of the extended cell death. As a reaction to this shrinkage, an increase in proliferation rate has been observed, *i.e.* the repopulation of a tumor (30). At the time this repopulation is initiated, treatment is generally still ongoing. Consequently, a higher dose is

required to kill the additional cancerous cells.

Repopulation can be incorporated into the Poisson TCP model by adding an exponential growth term to the cell survival equation

$$S = e^{-\alpha D - \beta G D^2} e^{\ln 2 \frac{(T - T_k)}{T_p}} \quad T > T_k \quad (2.10)$$

$$S = e^{-\alpha D - \beta G D^2} \quad T \leq T_k. \quad (2.11)$$

T_p is the proliferation doubling time, T the overall treatment time and T_k the off-set time for repopulation to initiate (31). A drawback of the Poisson TCP model is the lack of time dependency. For this reason, Zaider and Minerbo introduced an analytical expression for the TCP model with an explicit time dependency:

$$TCP(t) = \left[1 - \frac{S(t)e^{(b-d)t}}{1 + bS(t)e^{(b-d)t} \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{S(t')e^{(b-d)t'}}} \right]^{n_0} \quad (2.12)$$

(67). This formula is derived from a differential equation that expresses the change in the number of clonogenic cells as a function of natural formation b and death d rates, combined with the radiation-induced cell killing rate. The parameter S refers to cell survival and n represents the initial number of clonogenic cells. A time-dependent cell formation rate should be introduced to include an offset for repopulation. Moreover, this time-dependent TCP model should ideally be combined with an exponentially decreasing dose rate, as derived and presented by Zaider and Minerbo (67). Note that this model will result in a higher TCP compared to the time-independent expression proposed in equation (2.10) and that, in case $b = d = 0$, this expression will be reduced to the binomial TCP model (equation 2.2).

2.4.2 Heterogeneous Dose-Response

A heterogeneous dose-response should not be confused with dose heterogeneity, although both have an impact on TCP. In addition to dose heterogeneity, each tumor cell can also respond differently to the absorbed dose for various reasons. In regions with lower vascularisation, cells are more hypoxic and since oxygen can act as a radiosensitiser, those cells may be more radioresistant. Alpha particles and Auger electrons however are shown to be less affected by hypoxia (68). The radiosensitivity also varies throughout the cell cycle due to the availability of repair mechanisms, cell cycle checkpoints, mitotic catastrophe, etc. (33). Dawson and Hillen extended the time-dependent Zaider and Minerbo TCP model to include this cell cycle dependency (69). Herein the clonogenic cells were divided into a quiescent (G0) and active (G1, S, G2, M) phase, with a cell cycle phase-specific radiosensitivity. Cells can transfer from one phase to another over time and more compartments can be included if required.

Next to a heterogeneous radiosensitivity, tumor cell density is variable as well. A higher cell density requires a higher dose to account for additional clonogenic cells. However, a heterogeneous cell density has less impact on the TCP compared to heterogeneities in radiosensitivity (70).

It is important to consider tumor heterogeneity in a TCP model since a relapse occur from a niche of radioresistant cells or from the more dense tumoral subregions

(28, 67). One way to do this is via voxel control probabilities, similar to equation 2.7 for the dose heterogeneity. The global TCP is given by

$$TCP = \prod_i VCP(\alpha_i, \rho_i, D_i). \quad (2.13)$$

In the case of heterogeneous cell density, this model shows that the maximal TCP is achieved with a homogeneous VCP distribution (70). However, this is not the case for variations in radiosensitivity. In practice, the individual voxel radiosensitivities α_i and densities ρ_i can be obtained via various imaging methods (28). Although, a simplified model is often required because of the limitations of imaging. To simplify the model, one can split the tumor in oxic and hypoxic regions to account for differences in radiosensitivity between an oxic and hypoxic tumor environment. Another possibility is to introduce a probability distribution for radiosensitivity. Modeling cell survival according to a Gaussian distribution centered around an average α value with a variance of σ_α^2 results in

$$S = e^{-\alpha D - (\beta - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_\alpha^2)D^2} \quad (2.14)$$

(71). Note that the additional positive term $\frac{1}{2}\sigma_\alpha^2 D^2$ increases the cell survival and thus decreases TCP, as a consequence of the more radioresistant cells who have a larger impact on therapy efficacy compared to the more radiosensitive cells (see figure 2.1).

Ideally this heterogeneous dose-response should be correlated with the dose heterogeneity discussed in section 2.3.2.1 to make sure that intratumoral regions with a high absorbed dose overlap with the more radioresistant tumoral subregions. Unfortunately, those are generally inversely correlated because of perfusion (72). Regions with poor perfusion are more hypoxic and thus more radioresistant, as explained above, while at the same time, those regions will have a lower radiopharmaceutical uptake, and thus receive a lower absorbed dose.

2.4.3 Bystander Effect

The bystander effect refers to the phenomenon where non-irradiated cells show a dose-response relation due to cell-signalling from distantly irradiated cells, which is a well-recognised effect in EBRT. Due to the cross-fire effect, which is inherent to TRT and induces similar effects in distant cells, studying the bystander effect for TRT is more complicated(73). Nonetheless, bystander effects could be of large importance in TRT since it can induce effects in low dose regions and thereby reduce issues of dose-heterogeneity(49). To our knowledge, TCP models that incorporate the bystander effect have not been established so far.

2.5 Preclinical Dosimetry

While the administered activity is a more practical quantity to evaluate the treatment outcome, a more relevant parameter for evaluating radiobiological effects is the absorbed dose, amongst other important parameters such as dose rate, LET, heterogeneity and radiobiological parameters. Estimating the absorbed dose from an administered activity is unfortunately not straightforward and accurate data should be gathered regarding the RP uptake and distribution, cell/tissue geometries, combined with dose deposition simulations. Due to its complexity, dosimetry is often omitted in

preclinical research, or major assumptions are made, which results in substantial uncertainties.

These uncertainties might have a major impact on the interpretation of the observed effects, given that the TRT outcome depends on the absorbed dose. Konijnenberg *et al.* have shown that a commonly observed dose uncertainty of around 10% can result in differences in treatment outcome ranging from limited response ($TCP = 1\%$) up to almost complete remission ($TCP = 98\%$) (29). This points out the necessity for accurate preclinical dosimetry to correctly determine dose-effect relationships and to allow an objective and proper comparison of multiple treatments, both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

2.5.1 MIRD Scheme

The Medical Internal Radiation Dose (MIRD) Committee proposed the following scheme for calculating the absorbed dose D in a target region r_T from activity located in multiple source regions r_S :

$$D(r_T, T_D) = \sum_{r_S} \tilde{A}(r_S, T_D) S(r_T \leftarrow r_S) \quad (2.15)$$

(1). The definition of these regions is specific for each situation. For *in vivo* studies, these regions refer to whole organs or small voxels while in case of *in vitro* models, they refer to single cells or cell organelles. For each source region, the time integrated activity \tilde{A} is multiplied by the S-value. The former one represents the total number of radioactive decays within that source region r_S over the treatment time T_D , *i.e.* the activity integrated over time. The latter one is defined as the mean dose absorbed by the target region r_T per radioactive decay in the source region r_S . This factor depends on the specific geometry of the source and target region as well as on the radiation characteristics of the radionuclide. How this general scheme is applied in specific *in vitro* and *in vivo* situations is described in the subsequent sections.

2.5.2 In Vitro Dosimetry

In vitro studies are generally performed in the first stages of RP development and are the preferred method for determining radiobiological parameters and investigating biological mechanisms. However, the experimental conditions can vary substantially, which — in an ideal world — would require for the dosimetry to be repeated for each assay. An example of a standard radiobiological assay is the clonogenic survival assay. This assay generates the tumor cell survival curve, which provides important information on radiobiological parameters, including α and β , when presented as function of absorbed dose. A PubMed search resulted in 51 papers reporting a survival curve for radionuclide therapy. Eighteen of these studies (35%) did not perform dosimetry at all and reported survival in function of administered activity (23, 41, 74–89). However, Freudenberg *et al.* demonstrated how this can lead to a misinterpretation of the results (90). Plotting the cell survival in function of administered activity suggests a difference in effectiveness between various treatments, while similar effectiveness was observed after applying microdosimetry.

Five studies (10%) reported the cell survival in function of the bound activity per cell (91–94) or against the time integrated activity \tilde{A} (95). Taking this approach avoids

issues regarding cell saturation, making \tilde{A} a more relevant reference compared to the administered activity. However, to obtain the actual absorbed dose, one needs to still apply the appropriate S-values. About half of the studies, or 28 (55%) to be more specific, did perform dosimetry and reported cell survival as function of the average absorbed dose by the tumor cells, or more often, as a function of the absorbed dose by the cell nucleus. However, the accuracy of the applied dosimetry methods is debatable as often strong assumptions are made on the cell geometry (*e.g.* spherical cell geometry), RP distribution (*e.g.* uniform), RP clearance (*e.g.* no biological clearance) *etc.*

Figure 2.3: An overview of the evaluated dosimetry for cell survival curves. Fifty-one articles reporting a survival curve for TRT were evaluated. The survival curves were reported as a function of administered activity, bound activity or absorbed dose. The applied dosimetry often goes along with approximations such as neglecting biological decay, assuming spherical cells and nuclei or applying simplified dose deposition simulations instead of detailed Monte Carlo simulations.

2.5.2.1 *In Vitro* Source Regions

The standard source regions in *in vitro* assays are the medium (= non-specific dose), the neighbouring cells (= cross dose) and the cell organelles in the target cell (= self dose). Typically, the cell organelles to be considered are the cell membrane, the cytoplasm and the nucleus. Although activity uptake in the cell nucleus is limited for most vectors (46, 58), Falzone *et al.* have shown that even little uptake in the nucleus can induce a substantial increase in TCP, especially for particles with a short range such as Auger electrons (96). The available methods and techniques to access the subcellular activity distribution *in vitro* were recently reviewed by Costa *et al.* (97). The most common method by far is fractionation, in which the different physiochemical properties of the cell organelles of interest are exploited to obtain separated fractions, which subsequently can be measured with a gamma counter. Although fractionation is a fast, relatively easy and low-cost method, it provides only a population averaged distribution(97). In all 27 studies using dosimetry methods in this review, the activity is

assumed to be uniformly distributed within the cells. Nonetheless, both flow-cytometry results and autoradiography images showed that the RP uptake follows a log-normal instead of uniform distribution (98, 99). Rajon *et al.* showed with a computer model how such a log-normal distribution reduces the efficacy of a treatment (100).

2.5.2.2 Time Integrated Activity \tilde{A}

In order to access the time-integrated activity \tilde{A} , and thus the time-activity curve $A(r_s, t)$, the activity in each source region needs to be quantified at well-selected time points. Sufficient time points are required in order to fit the initial uptake and subsequent clearance phase accurately. Guirriero *et al.* investigated the effect of using different sets of time points and fitting models (7). They highlighted the importance of including late time points ($> 2 \times T_{1/2,eff}$) and pointed out the inaccuracy of using mono-exponential clearance models. Additionally, Sefl *et al.* showed that neglecting the initial uptake phase will lead to a substantial overestimation of the absorbed dose and thus an underestimation of cell survival (101). Nonetheless, 15 out of the 27 studies reporting survival vs dose (52%) evaluated the RP uptake at only a single time point and neglected biological decay, which can result in an overestimation of the absorbed dose (36, 40, 60, 62–64, 66, 90, 102–108).

2.5.2.3 S-Value

S-values should be determined for each cell-type, radionuclide and experimental set-up. Goddu *et al.* tabulated S-values for self-dose for various combinations, which were used in 30% of the studies performing dosimetry, whether or not extended by medium-dose simulations (109). Later on, a Java-applet MIRDcell was developed to calculate both self and cross dose S-values. Both Goddu and MIRDcell use a spherical geometry for the cells, combined with energy deposition based on the continuously slowing down approximation (110). The latter one is a semi-analytical method that neglects the finite range of secondary electrons and does not take into account straggling effects (111). At the sub-micron scale (*i.e.* subcellular level) it was shown that these approximations become inadequate, resulting in S-values who can differ by a factor of 2 compared to S-values obtained with Monte Carlo simulations, where a collision-by-collision approach is considered (112). These simulations require appropriate Monte Carlo particle transportation codes such as Geant4, MCNP, PENELOPE or GATE. Twelve authors (43%) did use such a code to compute detailed the dose deposition (40, 46, 57, 58, 61, 62, 65, 90, 102, 103, 113, 114).

Next to the computational methods that have been used, the geometry of the cell has also a large influence on the S-value. Twenty-four authors (86%) assumed concentric spherical cells and nuclei, despite the fact that cells are adherent during a colony survival assay and thus far from spherical. It has been demonstrated that a non-spherical cell (57) or an eccentric nucleus (115) may impact the absorbed dose significantly for short-range radiation. However, realistic cell geometry models are rather complex to implement. A first improvement on the standard concentric geometry was the usage of ellipsoids or oblate spheroids as an approximation for the cells and their nuclei, which was done by Steffen, Yard and Ruigrock (104, 114, 116). An even more realistic approximation was made by Tamborino *et al.*, who used the average S-value of 9 detailed polygonal mesh cell models based on confocal microscopy images (57). However, the S-values for those 9 models, representing

cells within a fixed cell line, showed a large variation. Finally, a completely different approach was taken by Palmer *et al.* who constructed distance probability density function (PDF) based on cell culture images (117). For each PDF bin, a dose point kernel needs to be applied only once, which substantially reduces the computational time.

For the cross dose, the distribution of cells within a culture plate is of more importance than the geometry of the cells itself. Generally, it is assumed that the cells are uniformly distributed, although some cell types tend to grow in clusters. Marcatili *et al.* developed a dosimetry framework for colony survival assays, including random cluster formation (118).

2.5.3 *In Vivo* Dosimetry

In vivo studies with appropriate animal models allow us to investigate a tumor microenvironment which is much more representative for the pathology in patients compared to *in vitro* assays. Organ-level activity distributions can be determined by either *ex vivo* biodistribution studies or *in vivo* nuclear molecular imaging techniques.

For the *ex vivo* approach, animals are sacrificed, organs of interest collected and subsequently weighted while organ activities are measured with a gamma counter. This procedure provides accurate activity concentrations for each organ. However, to determine the time-integrated organ and tumor activities, multiple animals need to be sacrificed at different time points to generate population averaged time activity curves for the tumor and organs of interest. Since a single time activity curve is based on the data of different animals, variability between animals induced by a different disease state or different tumor growth rate, can have a significant impact on final extracted time activity curve and thus on the dosimetry estimates which should therefore be interpreted with care. Moreover, *ex-vivo* biodistribution studies do not provide any information on the intra-organ or intra-tumoral activity distribution such that the effect of heterogeneous activity distributions cannot be taken into account.

On the other hand, autoradiography images are able to provide more detailed information about dose-distribution heterogeneities. Herein, the alpha or beta particle emissions from 2D cryosections are imaged with high resolution and provide quantitative activity distributions with a resolution up to 15 μm (119). The trade-off for these high resolution images is the missing 3D information, which limits the dosimetry. It is often assumed that the adjacent sections have identical activity distributions (44, 120). The recovered 3D activity map can then be convoluted with a dose point kernel (DPK) or direct Monte Carlo simulation can be performed in order to obtain the dose distribution. As an alternative to these autoradiographic images, immunofluorescent staining of the receptor also provides information on the activity distribution and has been used for dose calculations as well (43). Although this provides valuable information for the receptor heterogeneity, this does not take into account heterogeneity of the RP distributions, for example due to poor perfusion.

Meanwhile, *in vivo* molecular imaging techniques allow a non-invasive, quantitative assessment of the biodistribution of radiopharmaceuticals such that animals can be imaged multiple times to generate individual time activity curves. As such, dosimetry estimates will be much more consistent while therapy response can be monitored by a

longitudinal assessment of the tumor growth within the same animal. The most frequently used molecular imaging technique for dosimetry is Single Photon Emission Tomography (SPECT). This technique is also frequently used for dosimetry in clinical TRT, and was adapted for the smaller dimensions of mice and/or rats to provide adequate imaging performance for preclinical research. Consequently, *in vivo* preclinical SPECT imaging for dosimetry is also much more similar to the imaging approach used in clinic and therefore much more translatable. More specifically, preclinical or microSPECT (μ SPECT) is based on the detection of co-emitted gamma photons by the radionuclides and converts these detected gammas into a quantitative 3D activity distribution via iterative reconstruction algorithms (121). An additional Computerized Tomography (CT) scan provides anatomical information and allows to perform non-uniform attenuation and scatter correction, which improves the quantitative properties of the SPECT image. The CT scan is also beneficial for identifying the volumes of interest (VOI) in which the total activity concentration is determined. In addition, voxel activities reveal the heterogeneities on the sub-organ level. These are directly available from the quantitative μ SPECT/CT images, although the heterogeneity should be differentiated from the noise of the images itself (122). The voxel activities are limited by the resolution of SPECT images as well, which ranges from 5-25mm for clinical SPECT (121). However, the dimensions of small animals requires an even better resolution. This is achieved by the use of multipinhole collimators, resulting in a resolution of 1.5 mm (123). Those voxel activities should be converted to a voxel dose distribution. No tabulated voxel S-values are present for animal models, as is the case for clinical applications (124). An alternative is integration of DPK over the voxels with a CPU intensive conversion of spherical to Cartesian coordinates (125). This still does not take into account heterogeneities in tissue density, which asks for Monte Carlo simulations. Unfortunately, these require large computation times, which should be considered given the specific inaccuracy of DPK's .

For both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* methods, the conversion of the organ activities into absorbed doses requires organ S-values. These are available from software such as MIRDCalc, OLINDA and IDAC-dose, based on reference phantoms, or can be obtained via Monte Carlo simulations in combination with available digital animal models such as MOBY and ROBY (126).

To conclude, all these techniques are very complementary. Although the activities determined with μ SPECT are less accurate compared to *ex vivo* gamma counter measurements, μ SPECT allows to perform longitudinal studies within individual animals and enables a translation to clinical workflow. On the other hand, a single SPECT voxel has dimensions in the order of several mm^3 , such that activity can still be non-homogeneously distributed within one voxel. Meanwhile, *ex vivo* autoradiography images and *in vitro* dosimetry methods are able to provide valuable information regarding dose heterogeneity on subvoxel and subcellular level respectively. However, in *in vivo* studies a homogeneous dose within each voxel needs to be assumed since dose distributions at a voxel level are the highest achievable detail. On the other hand, subvoxel heterogeneities can clearly affect the treatment response which needs to be somehow incorporated in *in vivo* TCP models. A challenging task is thus to translate the effects of a subcellular and subvoxel dose heterogeneity up to the *in vivo* level.

2.6 Conclusion

Although the extension of TCP models towards TRT was established quite well from a theoretical viewpoint, sufficient confirmatory experimental data are still lacking. The low and protracted dose rate is understood to decrease the TCP, which can be quantified by the Lea-Catcheside factor. However, to our knowledge, the study by Tamborino *et al.* is the only study so far to actually include this factor in *in vivo* TCP models (43). In addition, the heterogeneous dose distribution, which is inherent to TRT, is expected to decrease the TCP, although prior research data are inconclusive due to contradictory results. The expected lower TCP because of dose heterogeneity could be partially compensated by the bystander effect, vascular damage, and anti-tumor immune responses as is observed in EBRT where an inhomogeneous dose from GRID therapy showed promising results (127). However, this not yet fully understood for TRT and actually quite hard to include in a TCP model since such a model hasn't been described so far. Moreover, the effect of the radiation quality, which should also be part of a TCP model, is quantified by RBE, which is a challenging quantity to be determined experimentally and therefore currently not accurate enough to actually be used in TCP models. In conclusion, additional comprehensive studies at the sub-cellular, cellular and organ level are essential to experimentally confirm the theoretical basis of TCP models for TRT and to gain further insight into TRT-specific quantities of these models.

Table 2.2: Overview of the RBE_m obtained via equation 2.9 for the 28 survival curves in function of absorbed dose discussed in section 2.5.2. For each RBE_m , details are given about the radionuclide, the cell type and the applied dosimetry (physical or effective decay for the Time Activity Constant (TAC), the cell geometry and the target region). The results are averaged for beta, Auger and alpha radiation and the standard deviation is reported.

Radionuclide	Cell line	TAC	Cell geometry	Target	RBE_m	Ref.
^{131}I	CA20948	T_{eff}	sphere	entire cell	1.2	(61)
^{177}Lu	U2OS + SSTR2	T_{eff}	realistic	nucleus	1.7	(57)
^{177}Lu	U2OS + SSTR2	T_{eff}	sphere	nucleus	0.5	(46)
^{177}Lu	CA20948	T_{eff}	sphere	nucleus	3.5	(46)
^{177}Lu	CA20948	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	0.4	(62)
^{177}Lu	Capan-2	T_{ph}	sphere	nucleus	1	(63)
^{177}Lu	LNCaP	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	0.4	(36)
^{177}Lu	DU145	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	1.5	(36)
^{177}Lu	PC3	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	1.5	(36)
^{32}P	SCL-II	T_{ph}	sphere	nucleus	0.5	(64)
^{90}Y	HCT116	T_{ph}	sphere	nucleus	0.2	(40)
^{90}Y	SW48	T_{ph}	sphere	nucleus	0.2	(40)
^{90}Y	HT29	T_{ph}	sphere	nucleus	0.2	(40)
Average RBE_{β}					1.0 ± 0.9	
^{123}I	PC Cl3	T_{eff}	sphere	nucleus	3.4	(58)
^{123}I	PC Cl3	T_{eff}	sphere	cytoplasm	1.7	(58)
^{123}I	PC Cl3	T_{eff}	sphere	entire cell	1.9	(58)
^{99m}Tc	PC Cl3	T_{eff}	sphere	nucleus	2.2	(58)
^{99m}Tc	PC Cl3	T_{eff}	sphere	cytoplasm	0.7	(58)
^{99m}Tc	PC Cl3	T_{eff}	sphere	entire cell	0.8	(58)
^{125}I	SCL-II	T_{ph}	sphere	nucleus	4.5	(64)
^{64}Cu	MCF7/HER2-18	T_{eff}	sphere	nucleus	0.6	(65)
Average RBE_{Auger}					2.0 ± 1.3	
^{213}Bi	CA20948	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	2.7	(62)
^{213}Bi	CA20948	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	3.5	(62)
^{213}Bi	Capan-2	T_{ph}	sphere	nucleus	3.4	(63)
^{241}Am	LNCaP	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	8.1	(36)
^{241}Am	DU145	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	15.2	(36)
^{241}Am	PC3	T_{ph}	sphere	entire cell	14.0	(36)
^{241}Am	SW-1573	T_{ph}	sphere	nucleus	14.7	(66)
Average RBE_{α}					8.8 ± 5.3	

Chapter 3

Aims & Objectives

The primary aim of this PhD research was to gain a better understanding of the absorbed dose-response relationships in TRT, and to explore how this is affected by TRT-specific irradiation characteristics such as the low absorbed dose-rate, the use of short-range particle irradiation and the heterogeneous absorbed dose distribution, both at tissue and subcellular level. The secondary aim was to identify the potential benefits of the novel radioisotope ^{161}Tb over the benchmark radioisotope ^{177}Lu and to evaluate if these potential benefits can be predicted by the TRT-specific absorbed dose-response model. To achieve these aims, the following objectives were addressed.

In **chapter 4**, we assessed the absorbed dose-response relationship of clonogenic cell survival *in vitro* after treatment with [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE, [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTA-LM3 or [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3. A comparison of these four absorbed dose-response relationships allowed to analyze both the advantage of the radioisotope ^{161}Tb as well as the impact of the subcellular absorbed dose heterogeneity (internalizing agonist DOTATATE vs. membrane bound antagonist DOTA-LM3). This analysis was supported with individual absorbed dose calculations per particle type, clearly demonstrating the distinct contributions of the β^- , IC and Auger electrons for each radio-peptide.

In **chapter 5**, we improved the established cellular absorbed dose-response curves from chapter 4 by replacing standard S-values that assumed spherical cells, with more accurate S-values that were simulated using virtual 3D cell models that better represented the adherent CA20948 cell geometry that has been used in the experiments. Besides improving our current understanding of the absorbed dose-response relationships, these virtual cell models also demonstrated the impact of shape modeling on cellular absorbed dose calculations and absorbed dose-response.

In **chapter 6**, we assessed the absorbed dose-response relationship of the tumor growth *in vivo* by means of a dose-escalating efficacy study with [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. By comparing these two absorbed dose-response relationships, we could further analyze the advantage of the radioisotope ^{161}Tb at a more clinically relevant scale. Furthermore, by comparing these tumor absorbed dose-response relationships with the previously determined cellular absorbed dose-response relationships, we could identify important aspects for a clinical translation of the TRT-specific absorbed dose-response.

In **chapter 6** we also created an analytical model that predicts the tumor growth based on the absorbed dose to the tumor. The input for this tumor-growth-model were the *in vitro* clonogenic survival (chapter 4), together with *ex vivo* absorbed dose distributions that were determined with digital autoradiography, and the model was validated against the experimental tumor growth curves of the efficacy study. With this tumor-growth-model, we could clearly demonstrate the impact absorbed dose heterogeneity at tissue level on tumor response.

Chapter 4

The Emission of Internal Conversion Electrons rather than Auger Electrons increased the Nucleus-Absorbed Dose for ^{161}Tb compared with ^{177}Lu with a Higher Dose-Response for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ than for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$

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Abstract

Preclinical data have shown that ^{161}Tb -labeled peptides targeting the somatostatin receptor are therapeutically more effective for peptide receptor radionuclide therapy than are their ^{177}Lu -labeled counterparts. To further substantiate this enhanced therapeutic effect, we performed cellular dosimetry to quantify the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus and compared dose–response curves to evaluate differences in relative biological effectiveness in vitro.

Methods: CA20948 cell survival was assessed after treatment with [^{161}Tb]Tb- and [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE (agonist) and with [^{161}Tb]Tb- and [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTA-LM3 (antagonist) via a clonogenic assay. Cell binding, internalization, and dissociation assays were performed up to 7d to acquire time-integrated activity coefficients. Separate S values for each type of particle emission (Auger/internal conversion [IC] electrons and β^- particles) were computed via Monte Carlo simulations, while considering spheric cells. Once the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus was calculated, survival curves were fitted to the appropriate linear or linear-quadratic model and corresponding relative biological effectiveness was evaluated.

Results: Although the radiopeptide uptake was independent of the radionuclide, [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 delivered a 3.6 and 3.8 times higher dose to the nucleus, respectively, than their ^{177}Lu -labeled counterparts on saturated receptor binding. This increased nucleus-absorbed dose was mainly due to the additional emission of IC and not Auger electrons by ^{161}Tb . When activity concentrations were considered, both [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 showed a lower survival fraction than did labeling with ^{177}Lu . When the absorbed dose to the nucleus was considered, no significant difference could be observed between the dose–response curves for [^{161}Tb]Tb- and [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE. [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 showed a linear-quadratic dose-response, whereas [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE showed only a linear dose-response within the observed dose range, suggesting additional cell membrane damage by Auger electrons.

Conclusion: The IC, rather than Auger, electrons emitted by ^{161}Tb resulted in a higher absorbed dose to the cell nucleus and lower clonogenic survival for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 than for the ^{177}Lu -labeled analogs. In contrast, [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE showed no higher dose-response than [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE, whereas for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 an additional quadratic response was observed. Because of this quadratic response, potentially caused by cell membrane damage, [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 is a more effective radiopeptide than [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE for labeling with ^{161}Tb .

4.1 Introduction

Currently, [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTA-[Tyr3]octreotate ([^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE) is the standard clinical peptide receptor radionuclide therapy for patients with unresectable or metastatic, progressive, and somatostatin receptor type 2 (SSTR2)-positive gastroenteropancreatic neuroendocrine tumors, as approved by both the European Medicines Agency (2017) and the American Food and Drug Administration (2018). It combines ^{177}Lu , a low-energy β^- -emitter, with the SSTR2-agonist octreotate, which has shown therapeutic efficacy, as first demonstrated in the NETTER-1 clinical trial (14). Meanwhile, ^{161}Tb has been identified as a highly promising radioisotope for β^- -therapy, with a half-life and a β^- -emission spectrum comparable to those of ^{177}Lu . In addition, ^{161}Tb emits per nuclear transition on average 1.4 internal conversion (IC) and 11 Auger electrons, compared with 0.15 IC and 1 Auger electron per ^{177}Lu decay (Supplemental Fig. A.2 shows the spectra in detail). These additional low-energy electrons are anticipated to enhance therapeutic efficacy because of their shorter range and higher linear energy transfer.

The β^- , IC, and Auger electron emissions of ^{161}Tb have an average range in water of 301 μm (continuously-slowng-down approximation), 13 μm , and 97 nm, respectively (estimated with the Geant4 example “range” (4, 128, 129)), which makes them particularly effective for treating small metastases, as demonstrated by the metastatic model of Bernhardt et al. (26). The high linear energy transfer of Auger electrons is expected to induce more complex DNA damage, thereby resulting in a higher biological effectiveness when emitted near nuclear DNA (130). Not only the nuclear DNA but also the cell membrane was shown to be radiosensitive to Auger electrons (131). Accordingly, cell membrane-binding antagonists were found to benefit more from the Auger electrons emitted by ^{161}Tb than do internalizing agonists (23).

Numerous studies, both in vitro and in vivo, consistently reported a higher therapeutic effectiveness for ^{161}Tb -labeled radiopharmaceuticals than for their ^{177}Lu -labeled counterparts for equivalent administered activities (23, 132, 133). In addition, Monte Carlo simulations have revealed that, for identical administered activities, ^{161}Tb yielded a higher absorbed dose than ^{177}Lu (134). However, these individual reports on the therapeutic response and dosimetry did not provide conclusive evidence of the increased biological effectiveness of ^{161}Tb - versus ^{177}Lu -labeled peptide. Therefore, the aim of this paper was to evaluate the biological effectiveness in vitro by establishing dose-response relationships for the radiolabeled SSTR2 agonists [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and antagonists [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3, to determine which combination proved to be the most effective for peptide receptor radionuclide therapy and the better option for clinical translation.

4.2 Materials and Methods

4.2.1 Cell Culture and Radiolabeling

CA20948 cells were kindly provided by Prof. Julie Nonnekens (Erasmus MC) (135) and cultured with Dulbecco modified Eagle medium at 37°C and 5% CO_2 . CA20948 cells ($2 \cdot 10^5$) were seeded in 12-well plates the day before the treatments to allow for

adherence. Radiolabeling was done at a ^{161}Tb or ^{177}Lu concentration of 400 MBq/mL in 0.1 M NaOAc (pH 4.7) for 15 min at 90°C to obtain a molar activity of 100 MBq/nmol. The radiochemical purity was checked with instant thin-layer chromatography after each radiolabeling (>95%). The radiolytic stability was verified by high-performance liquid chromatography (>90% after 6 h). The precursors DOTATATE (ABX) and DOTA-LM3 (MedChemExpress) were radiolabeled with no-carrier-added ^{177}Lu (ITM) and no-carrier-added ^{161}Tb (SCK CEN). All compounds were used without additional purification.

4.2.2 Colony Survival Assay

The reproductive cell survival after radioligand treatment was evaluated with a colony survival assay. CA20948 cells were incubated for 4 h with a range of activity concentrations (from 1.22 to 1,250 kBq/mL), after which the cells were trypsinized and seeded in a 6-well plate in triplicate (300 cells per well). After 14 d, the colonies (≥ 50 cells per colony) were fixed and stained with 6% glutaraldehyde and 0.5% crystal violet. The plates were imaged with the transmission light of Fusion FX (Vilber), and colonies were counted with the Analyse Particles function in ImageJ software after thresholding (136). Finally, the number of colonies was normalized to a control condition to obtain the percentage of survival.

4.2.3 Uptake Assays

A saturation binding experiment was performed for activity concentrations from 0.01 to 5 MBq/mL. The results were fitted to the one-site total and nonspecific binding model of Prism (GraphPad):

$$B_{4h}(a) = \frac{B_{max} \cdot a}{K_d + a} + NS \cdot a, \quad (4.1)$$

where B_{4h} is the number of bound radiopharmaceuticals per cell after 4 h; a is the activity concentration; and B_{max} , K_d and NS are fitting parameters representing the maximal specific binding, affinity, and nonspecific binding, respectively. The association and dissociation kinetics were assumed to be independent of the isotope and were determined with only ^{161}Tb - and ^{177}Lu -labeled peptides, respectively. In both uptake assays, the cell membrane and the internalized and medium fractions were collected. More details are described in the supplemental materials (23, 137).

4.2.4 Cellular Dosimetry

The average absorbed dose to the cell nuclei during the colony survival assay was determined for each added activity concentration a on the basis of the formalism of the MIRD committee (1):

$$D_{nucleus}(a) = \sum_{r_s} \tilde{A}_{r_s}(a) \cdot S_{r_s}. \quad (4.2)$$

The considered source regions r_s were the cytoplasm, the cell membrane, the neighboring cells, and the activity in the culture medium. The time-integrated activity coefficients \tilde{A} are the total number of nuclear decays within a source region and were based on the data from the saturation binding and kinetic uptake assay. These were multiplied by the corresponding S-values, which are the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus per decay within a source region. The S values were simulated with the

Monte Carlo particle transportation code Geant4 for a spheric geometry. More detailed information can be found in the supplemental materials (129, 138–141).

4.2.5 Radiobiologic Parameters

The dose–response relationships were obtained by plotting the cell survival fractions against the absorbed doses to the cell nucleus. The linear-quadratic (LQ) model describes the dose–response as follows:

$$S_{LQ}(D) = e^{-\alpha D - \beta D^2} \quad (4.3)$$

where α represents the cell radiosensitivity to the radiation and β accounts for superposition of radiation damage. In targeted radionuclide therapy, the quadratic contribution is generally so low that the dose–response relationship can often be described by a linear (L) model:

$$S_L(D) = e^{-\alpha D}. \quad (4.4)$$

Both models were fitted with nonlinear regression to the dose–response data, and selection of the best fit was based on the extra-sum-of-squares F test. The fitted α and β values were used to calculate the relative biological effectiveness (RBE),

$$RBE_X = \frac{D_{ref}(S = X)}{D(S = X)}, \quad (4.5)$$

which is the absorbed dose of a reference radiation over the dose of the investigated radiation type that induces an equal biological effect, which was here a survival fraction X , with $X = 10\%$ or $X = 50\%$. When possible, the RBE_{max} , which is the RBE extrapolated to 100% survival, was also calculated as

$$RBE_{max} = \frac{\alpha}{\alpha_{ref}} \quad (4.6)$$

An external ^{137}Cs source (γ of 662 keV, 0.6 Gy/min) was used to calculate D_{ref} with the α and β for the CA20948 cells taken from Chan et al. (62).

4.2.6 Statistical Methods

An unpaired parametric t test and 2-way ANOVA were used to test for statistical significance, with the significance level (α) set to 0.05 (Prism). Curves were fitted with least squares regression, and selection of the best fit was based on the extra-sum-of-squares F test, which was also used to compare and check whether 2 data sets could be fit with a single curve. The curve fitting returned the standard error for the estimated fitting parameters, which was used to calculate the error on the final absorbed dose via standard error propagation rules. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD from $N = 3$ technical replicates and $n = 3$ biological replicates, unless otherwise stated.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Clonogenic Survival

Clonogenic survival was significantly reduced after treatment with at least a 0.02 MBq/mL dose of $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ or $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ in comparison with

untreated controls ($P < 0.0003$, $P < 0.0001$), whereas for [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE this reduction was significant from 0.08 MBq/mL ($P < 0.02$) onward and for [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTA-LM3 for a concentration of 0.16 and 1.25 MBq/mL ($P = 0.012$, $P = 0.03$, 2-way ANOVA, Fig. 4.1). Treatment with [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and -DOTA-LM3 significantly reduced clonogenic survival compared with the ^{177}Lu -labeled analogs for activity concentrations higher than 0.04 and 0.02 MBq/mL, respectively ($P < 0.014$, $P < 0.027$). No significant difference was observed between [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3, whereas for [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE a significantly lower clonogenic survival was observed at 0.625 and 1.25 MBq/mL than for [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTA-LM3 ($P = 0.02$, $P = 0.01$).

Figure 4.1: Clonogenic survival of CA20948 cells after treatment with [^{161}Tb]Tb- and [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and -DOTA-LM3 as function of added activity concentration (MBq/mL). Error bars are defined as ± 1 SD ($N = 3$, $n = 6$).

4.3.2 Saturation Binding and Uptake Kinetics

The saturation binding results are visualized in Figure 4.2, whereas fitting parameters are summarized in Supplemental Table A.1. No significant differences in B_{max} , K_d , or NS were observed between ^{161}Tb - and ^{177}Lu -labeled analogs; thus, data were pooled for further analysis. Primarily specific, saturable binding was observed, setting an upper limit to the self-dose achievable with a fixed molar activity. A maximum concentration of 12.5 nM was selected for the colony-forming assay so that the binding would not surpass 90% of the B_{max} to avoid an increased dose contribution from the radioactive medium. [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 showed a slightly lower B_{max} than did [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE ($P = 0.04$, $B_{max} = 0.78 \pm 0.14$ vs. $1.1 \pm 0.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ fmol/cell), whereas their affinity was significantly higher ($P = 0.0012$, $K_d = 0.19 \pm 0.05$ vs. 1.0 ± 0.4 nM). Nevertheless, the major difference was the higher internalized fraction of [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE (86.4%) than of [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 (10.5%).

Figure 4.2: Saturation binding assay representing total binding and nonspecific binding for different added activity concentrations of $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ with fixed molar activity of 100 MBq/nmol. Error bars are defined as ± 1 SD ($N = 3$, $n = 3$).

Figure 4.3 shows the association and dissociation kinetics, along with the fitted curves of the equations (Supplemental Eqs. 5–8). After the incubation phase, $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ showed an exponential excretion of the activity over time, whereas $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ showed an initial internalization before excretion into the medium. The association kinetics of $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ were not significantly different from those of $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ (Supplemental Tab. A.1). The final time–activity curves were obtained after decay correction and a correction for cell division with a doubling time of 28 ± 0.02 h (Supplemental Fig. A.1).

Figure 4.3: (A) Association kinetics during 4 h of incubation with 0.024, 0.78 and 12.5 nM $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$. (B and C) Dissociation kinetics of 1 nM $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ (B) and $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTA-LM3}$ (C) for all compartments (internalized, cell membrane, and medium fraction). Error bars are defined as ± 1 SD ($N = 3$, $n = 2$).

4.3.3 Absorbed Dose to the Nucleus

The S values for the dose to the nucleus are summarized in Supplemental Table A.2 for each source region, radioisotope, and particle separately. For ^{177}Lu , the highest nuclear S values correspond to the emitted β^- particles, whereas for ^{161}Tb , IC electrons have the largest contribution. The difference between the nuclear S values from the cytoplasm S_{cyto} and the cell membrane S_{CM} was relatively low for β^-

particles and IC electrons ($\frac{S_{CM}}{S_{Cyto}} = 50\%–70\%$), whereas S_{cyto} was 24 and 19 times higher than S_{CM} for the Auger electrons emitted by ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb , respectively. Plotting the total absorbed dose against the activity concentration (Fig. 4.4) revealed a nonlinear and saturable relationship. At higher activity concentrations, radiolabeled DOTATATE resulted in a higher absorbed dose than did radiolabeled DOTA-LM3, because of DOTATATE's higher B_{max} and higher internalization (Fig. 4.5B). Note that the contribution of the cytoplasm to the absorbed dose in the cell nucleus was still 47% (5.9 Gy/12.5 Gy) and 43% (1.4 Gy/3.4 Gy) for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTA-LM3 and $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTA-LM3, respectively, because of the internalization over time. At lower activity concentrations, the absorbed dose of radiolabeled DOTA-LM3 was higher than that of radiolabeled DOTATATE because of its higher affinity. However, the most significant difference was observed between $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTATATE and $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTATATE and between $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTA-LM3 and $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTA-LM3, with an average increase of 3.6 and 3.8, respectively. The increased nucleus-absorbed dose of the ^{161}Tb -labeled peptides was primarily due to the additional emission of IC electrons by ^{161}Tb (Fig. 4.5A) and not by the Auger electrons.

Figure 4.4: Total absorbed dose to cell nucleus for range of added activity concentrations of both ^{161}Tb - and ^{177}Lu -labeled DOTATATE and DOTA-LM3. Error bands represent ± 1 SD.

4.3.4 Dose-Response

The nuclear dose–response data of both $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ - and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTATATE were best fitted with a linear model and could be fitted with a common, single curve ($P = 0.24$; Fig. 4.6A). This indicated that there was no significant difference between the dose–response relationships of $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ - and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTATATE, which was reflected in comparable RBE values (Tab. 4.1). On the other hand, within the limited dose range, $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTA-LM3 fitted better to a linear-quadratic model, whereas $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTA-LM3 was best described by the linear model. Because the best-fitting model was different for both data sets, a direct comparison was not feasible (Fig. 4.6B). In addition, because of the limited dose range, and corresponding high survival

Figure 4.5: Absorbed dose to cell nucleus, corresponding to 1 MBq/mL of respective radioligands depicted in x-axis, and contributions from different particles (A) and source regions (B). Error bars are defined as ± 1 SD of total absorbed dose calculated over all particle types or all source regions.

fractions, the RBE values with survival fractions of 10% or 50% for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTA-LM3}$ were not reported.

The dose–response data of $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTA-TATE}$ and $-DOTA-LM3$ were better fitted with 2 separate linear curves, indicating a significantly higher dose-response for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTA-TATE}$ ($P < 0.0001$; Fig. 4.6C). In addition, $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-TATE}$ and $-DOTA-LM3$ were also better fitted with 2 separate dose–response curves ($P < 0.0001$), confirming a higher dose-response for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ than for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-TATE}$ in the higher absorbed-dose range (Fig. 4.6D). However, for an absorbed dose below 6.9 ± 0.3 Gy, the dose-response of $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ was lower than that of $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-TATE}$ (Fig. 4.6D). These observations are again reflected in the calculated RBE values. Note that all RBE values were estimated as lower than 1, indicating a lower dose-response than the reference ^{137}Cs irradiation.

Table 4.1: Fitting Parameters of survival Curves

Parameter	$^{177}\text{Lu-DOTA-TATE}$	$^{161}\text{Tb-DOTA-TATE}$	$^{177}\text{Lu-DOTA-LM3}$	$^{161}\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$
Best fit [†]	Linear	Linear	Linear	Linear-quadratic
α (Gy^{-1})	0.100 ± 0.012	0.111 ± 0.005	0.049 ± 0.009	0.000 ± 0.025
β (Gy^{-2})	–	–	–	0.017 ± 0.004
$\text{RBE}_{\text{max}}^{\ddagger}$	0.48 ± 0.17	0.53 ± 0.18	0.23 ± 0.09	– [‡]
RBE_{50}	0.31 ± 0.11	0.35 ± 0.12	– [§]	0.33 ± 0.12
RBE_{10}	– [§]	0.24 ± 0.05	– [§]	0.42 ± 0.08

*Based on extra-sum-squares F test.

[†]Reference source for RBE was ^{137}Cs source ($\alpha = 0.21(7) \text{ Gy}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.05(2) \text{ Gy}^{-2}$ from Chan et al. (62)).

[‡] RBE_{max} not valid for $\alpha = 0$

[§]Because this radioligand did not reach 50% or 10% survival in colony survival assay, corresponding RBE value was not calculated.

RBE_{50} and RBE_{10} are RBE's with survival fractions of 10% and 50%, respectively

Figure 4.6: Clonogenic survival curves plotted against absorbed dose in cell nucleus (Gy), shown per peptide (A and B) or per radioisotope (C and D). All data are fitted to linear model except for ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTA-LM3, which is fitted to linear-quadratic model. Fitting parameters are summarized in Table 1. Error bars correspond to ± 1 SD, whereas error bands represent 95% confidence interval of curve fit.

4.4 Discussion

In previous work, it was shown that treatment with ^{161}Tb -labeled peptides reduced cell survival compared with ^{177}Lu -labeled analogs for the same activity concentration (8–10). Simulations have also shown that the ^{161}Tb emission spectrum resulted in a higher cellular absorbed dose than did the ^{177}Lu emission spectrum (11). Both findings were confirmed by this study for ^{177}Lu - and ^{161}Tb -labeled DOTATATE and DOTA-LM3. In addition, the aim of this study was to extend these findings and compare their dose–response curves and subcellular dose distributions.

We did not observe a significant difference in dose–response between ^{177}Lu Lu- and ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE, as can be explained by the intracellular dose distributions of the different types of particle emissions. The increased absorbed dose to the nucleus for ^{161}Tb -labeled agonists and antagonists originated predominantly from the higher fraction of IC electron emissions by ^{161}Tb , rather than from the Auger electron emissions. Although IC and Auger electrons are often grouped together, their differences in energy result in a different range and linear energy transfer and, consequently, in a different dose distribution and dose–response. More specifically, the range of the Auger electrons was too short (nm range), compared with the

CA20948 cell geometry (μm range), to substantially contribute to the absorbed dose to the nucleus from within the cytoplasm or from the cell membrane. Hence, close subcellular targeting (nm range) of radiosensitive structures remains indispensable to exploit the full potential of Auger-emitting radioisotopes, such as ^{161}Tb . Meanwhile, the additional emission of IC electrons by ^{161}Tb resulted in a higher absorbed dose to the cell nucleus but not in a higher dose-response, indicating that IC electrons have a similar biological effectiveness as β^- particles. Nonetheless, the higher absorbed dose per nuclear transition for ^{161}Tb than for ^{177}Lu because of the emission of IC electrons is important when receptors are saturated, which allows delivery of a higher cellular absorbed dose and thus a more effective treatment.

$[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTA-LM3 showed a linear-quadratic dose-response relationship for the nucleus, whereas the nuclear dose-response of $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTATATE had only a linear component. Since $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTA-LM3 was initially bound to the cell membrane, the emission of Auger electrons by ^{161}Tb likely caused additional cell membrane damage, resulting in a quadratic dependence of survival on the absorbed dose in the nucleus. Cell membrane damage by Auger electron emissions was also reported by Pouget et al. (131) and has been shown to induce bystander effects in nontargeted cells, which might contribute to the quadratic response (142, 143). However, this remains a hypothesis and should be clarified by additional experiments to measure cell membrane damage in combination with cell membrane dosimetry, considering the small dimensions of the cell membrane (7.5–10 nm), the variable location of the radionuclide relative to the membrane, and the short range and cascade behavior of Auger electrons.

When comparing ^{177}Lu -labeled DOTA-LM3 and DOTATATE, we observed a higher nuclear dose-response for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTATATE, indicating that β^- particles caused more lethal cell damage when emissions were near the nucleus, despite their larger range. However, within the colony-forming assay, the trypsinization of the cells might have cleaved a portion of the SSTR2 after the peptide binding (144), resulting in lower binding within the clonogenic assay and thus an overestimation of the actual absorbed dose in the nucleus. This overestimation would be more prominent for the membrane-bound $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTA-LM3, meaning that the actual dose-response relationships for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTA-LM3 and $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTATATE are probably more similar, as could be expected. This might also explain the observed higher dose-response for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTATATE than for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb}$ -DOTA-LM3 in the lower dose range. The trypsinization of the cells might also have led to selection of the least damaged cells, thereby underestimating survival for all radiopeptides (145). Treating the cells after seeding may circumvent this issue.

When we compared our findings with literature values, we found that Chan et al. obtained a lower radiosensitivity ($\alpha = 0.08$) for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu}$ -DOTATATE than we did ($\alpha = 0.100 \pm 0.012$), and they also observed a quadratic component ($\beta = 0.003$) (62). O'Neill et al. reported a much higher value ($\alpha = 0.63 \pm 0.07$, $\beta < 10^{-6}$) (46). Both studies considered only physical decay, whereas radioligand dissociation from the cell and cell division were neglected, potentially overestimating the absorbed dose and underestimating the radiosensitivity. Moreover, O'Neill et al. extrapolated uptake data to lower activity concentrations. Therefore, relating our findings to previously reported findings is not straightforward.

4.5 Conclusion

Cellular dosimetry and cell survival assays showed that [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 resulted in a higher absorbed dose to the cell nucleus and a lower clonogenic survival than did the ^{177}Lu -labeled analogs for the same activity. In addition, Monte Carlo simulations demonstrated that IC electrons contributed predominantly to the increased absorbed dose to the cell nucleus of ^{161}Tb -labeled DOTATATE and DOTA-LM3, and the range of Auger electrons was too limited to contribute to the cell nucleus-absorbed dose. Evaluation of the dose-response curves revealed that ^{161}Tb instead of ^{177}Lu labeling did not significantly alter the dose-response for DOTATATE. On the other hand, the antagonist [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 increased the biological effectiveness compared with the agonist [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE for higher nucleus-absorbed doses, as indicated by the linear-quadratic dose-response relationship. This higher dose-response may be due to the high membrane-bound fraction of [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 and the emission of Auger electrons by ^{161}Tb , causing additional damage to the cell membrane. As a result, the SSTR2 antagonist [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 proved to be a more therapeutically effective peptide for labeling with ^{161}Tb than did the agonist [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, making [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 the preferred combination for clinical translation.

Chapter 5

Realistic versus Spherical Cellular Geometry Models: Impact on Dose–Response of CA20948 Cells to ^{177}Lu - and ^{161}Tb -Labeled DOTATATE and DOTA-LM3

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Abstract

Accurate cellular dosimetry is essential to investigate fundamental mechanisms of targeted radionuclide therapy. The aim of this study was to assess how realistic cellular geometry models influence cellular dosimetry estimates, in comparison to simplified spherical models that do not properly represent an adherent cell geometry.

Methods Virtual cell models of the CA20948 cell line were generated by confocal microscopy of SSTR2 and DAPI staining, and served as input to derive realistic S-values for ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb . Absorbed dose–response relationships were established for ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE, ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE, ^{177}Lu Lu-DOA-LM3 and ^{161}Tb Tb-DOA-LM3 using S-values from both realistic and spherical cell geometries.

Results Thirty-four cell geometries were modeled and a spherical model with equivalent volume was generated with a radius for the cell and nucleus of 8.6(7) μm and 5.5(6) μm , respectively. Compared to spherical cell models, realistic cell models significantly changed the S-value with an increase of 13 % (^{177}Lu) and 22 % (^{161}Tb) with the cell membrane as source region and a decrease of 11 % (^{177}Lu) and 12 % (^{161}Tb) with the cytoplasm as source region. Absorbed dose-response relationships based on realistic cell geometries showed a linear dose-response model for ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE and ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE with $\alpha = 0.22(2) \text{ Gy}^{-1}$, and a linear-quadratic dose-response model for ^{177}Lu Lu-DOA-LM3 and ^{161}Tb Tb-DOA-LM3 with $\alpha = 0.00(2) \text{ Gy}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.064(8) \text{ Gy}^{-2}$. The assumption of

a spherical cell model did not significantly affect the dose-response models, while underestimating the cell dimensions did induce a scaling to the dose-response models.

Conclusion These findings support the use of spherical cellular geometries as a valid simplified dosimetry model to compare radiopharmaceuticals using the same cell line. Comparing dose-response relationships using different cell lines warrants more realistic models to account for differences in cellular geometry and cell dimensions.

5.1 Introduction

Radiobiological assessments within targeted radionuclide therapy (TRT) rely to a large extent on 2D *in vitro* evaluations. Clonogenic survival assays, for example, are key experiments to assess the radiosensitivity of different cell types to various radiation treatments. Such radiobiological assessments become even more relevant when evaluating responses in function of absorbed doses with the reliability and translatability toward *in vivo* or clinical scale largely depending on the accuracy of absorbed dose calculations.

Estimations of the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus often assume spherical cells and nuclei, however, this does not properly represent the adherent cell geometry. Tamborino *et al.* created realistic virtual cell models for the U2OS human osteosarcoma cell type, and thereby showed a major impact of the cell volume (inverse exponential trend) and shape modeling (up to 65 %) (57).

Therefore, this study created more realistic cell models for adherent CA20948 cells, a rat pancreatic cell line that overexpresses the somatostatin receptor 2 (SSTR2), and that is therefore frequently used to investigate Peptide Receptor Radionuclide Therapy (PRRT) (135). This cell type was recently utilized to evaluate the absorbed dose-response relationship of ^{177}Lu - and ^{161}Tb -radiolabelled agonists (DOTA-TATE¹) and antagonists (DOTA-LM3²)(146). Based on the developed realistic cell model, we calculated S-values for the radioisotopes ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb through Monte-Carlo simulations, and compared dose-response curves of ^{177}Lu - and ^{161}Tb -labeled DOTA-TATE and DOTA-LM3 using these more realistic S-values with the dose-response curves that were determined with S-values that were based on a simplified spherical cell model. As such, the aim of this study was to determine whether simplified spherical geometries are sufficient for accurate cellular dosimetry or if more realistic adherent cell models are required.

5.2 Materials & Methods

5.2.1 Antibody Staining, Imaging and Segmentation

CA20948 cells were seeded in an 8-well chamber-slide (Ibidi, Germany), and after 24 h cells stained with a SSTR2a primary antibody (rabbit monoclonal; Ab134152, Abcam) and Alexa fluor 568 secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit; A11011 Thermo

¹DOTA-Tyr3-octreotate

²DOTA-[p-CI-Phe-cyclo(D-Cys-Tyr-D-4-amino-Phe(carbamoyl)-Lys-Thr-Cys)D-Tyr-NH2]

Fisher Scientific) to identify the cell membrane. In addition, DAPI counterstaining was used to highlight the cell nucleus, after performing fixation with 2 % PFA, permeabilisation with 0.1 % PBS-T and blocking with 5 % bovine serum albumin. Cells were imaged using a confocal microscope ($\Delta z = 1 \mu\text{m}$ using a Zeiss LSM 880, Cell and Tissue Imaging Core, KU Leuven). Cell membrane and cell nucleus were segmented based on the SSTRa and DAPI stained 3D images of the cells using 3D Slicer (Fig 5.1).

Figure 5.1: A representative image of (a) SSTR2a (red) and DAPI (blue) staining, (b) segmentation of the cell membrane (yellow), nucleus (blue) and cytoplasm (red) and (c) 3D reconstruction of the nuclear (pink) and cytoplasm (orange) segmentations.

5.2.2 S-Value Simulations

The segmentation of the cell membrane, cytoplasm and cell nucleus of $n = 34$ randomly selected cells were used as input for Monte Carlo simulations using GATE (147) to compute realistic S-values for the absorbed dose evaluated to the cell nucleus. A minimum of 20 cells were needed to derive an average S-value with a 95 % confidence interval of $[S \pm 10 \text{ \%}]$. The emission spectra for the β^- , internal conversion (IC) and Auger electrons of ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb were taken from ICRP107 (4), and activities were assigned uniformly either to the cell membrane or within the cytoplasm. The average volume of the cell and cell nucleus of the realistic cell models was also calculated, and used as input to calculate S-values for a spherical model of the cell and nucleus with equivalent volumes. For the spherical model, we considered either a uniform activity and the absorbed dose to the entire cell (later referred to as 'uniform sphere') or the activity distributed on the cell membrane or in the cytoplasm and only the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus.

5.2.3 Radiosensitivity Evaluation

Absorbed doses to the cell nucleus were calculated with the more realistic S-values for CA20948 cells to estimate cell-radiosensitivity parameters from the clonogenic assay, performed on CA20948 cells that were treated with either $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTA-TATE}$, $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-TATE}$, $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTA-LM3}$ or $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$, as extensively described in (146). For the absorbed dose calculations, association kinetics up to 4 h, dissociation kinetics up to 7 d, cell binding properties determined from saturation binding assays and internalization kinetics up to 7 d were considered to calculate the contributions from self dose, cross-dose and

dose from the medium. The resulting absorbed dose-response curves were fitted to either a linear

$$S(D) = e^{-\alpha \cdot D} \quad (5.1)$$

or linear-quadratic

$$S(D) = e^{-\alpha \cdot D - \beta \cdot D^2} \quad (5.2)$$

dose-response model, depending on which model was selected by the extra-sum-of-square F-test. For dose-response curves with a common best-fit model, a fit to a shared curve was evaluated using the extra-sum-of-square F-test, to determine whether a difference in absorbed dose-response could be confirmed. Statistical significance was considered from $p = 0.05$. Results were compared with findings from a previous study (146), where spherical instead of realistic S-values were considered, to calculate the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus for generating the absorbed dose-response curves. Dose-response curves were again compared by the extra-sum-of-square F-test.

5.3 Results

The staining and segmentation (Fig. 5.1) of CA20948 cells ($n = 34$) resulted in an average cell and nucleus volume of $2629(663) \mu\text{m}^3$ and $689(211) \mu\text{m}^3$ with equivalent spherical radii of $8.6(7) \mu\text{m}$ and $5.5(6) \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The different cell shapes and dimensions resulted in a large variation of S-values, with all S-values significantly different from S-values based on spherical geometries (Tab. 5.1, Fig. 5.2). The use of realistic cell models resulted in a significantly increased S-value for the cell membrane (13 % for ^{177}Lu and 22 % for ^{161}Tb) and a significantly decreased S-value for the cytoplasm (11 % for ^{177}Lu and 12 % for ^{161}Tb), compared to the use of a spherical cell model where the uniform model largely overestimated the S-values, especially for the internal conversion (IC) and Auger electrons.

Table 5.1: The average realistic self-dose S-values for CA20948 cells in $\mu\text{Gy Bq}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{cell}^{-1} \pm$ standard deviation ($n = 34$ cells).

Isotope	Particle	Uniform	Cell Membrane → nucleus			Cytoplasm → nucleus		
			Realistic	Sphere	p-value	Realistic	Sphere	p-value
^{161}Tb	Beta	199	104(20)	92	0.002	133(26)	151	0.0004
^{161}Tb	IC	707	348(81)	282	0.00004	463(106)	536	0.0004
^{161}Tb	Auger	495	10(8)	4	0.00003	40(13)	33	0.003
^{161}Tb	All	1401	463(105)	378	0.00005	637(144)	720	0.002
^{177}Lu	Beta	227	116(23)	102	0.0011	150(30)	171	0.0003
^{177}Lu	IC	32	18(3)	17	0.012	22(4)	25	0.00015
^{177}Lu	Auger	58.5	1.9(13)	0.5	< 0.00001	6(2)	5.2	0.005
^{177}Lu	All	317	136(26)	120	0.0008	179(36)	201	0.0009

The corresponding absorbed dose-response curves for realistic cell geometries are shown in figure 5.3. The dose-response curves for [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE were best fitted with a shared ($p = 0.29$) linear ($p = 0.9$ and $p = 0.4$, respectively) absorbed dose-response curve with $\alpha = 0.22(2) \text{ Gy}^{-1}$. [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTA-LM3 and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 were better fitted to a shared ($p = 0.7$) linear-quadratic ($p = 0.04$ and $p < 0.0001$, respectively) survival curve with $\alpha = 0.00(2) \text{ Gy}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.064(8) \text{ Gy}^{-2}$. When comparing these absorbed dose-response curve fits with those when assuming an equivalent spherical model (Fig. 5.3 solid vs

Figure 5.2: The self-dose S-values for a uniform spherical (uniform activity distribution and absorbed dose evaluation) and a spherical or realistic CA20948 cell model with activity distributed either on the cell membrane (CM) or in the cytoplasm (Cyto), and the absorbed dose evaluated in the cell nucleus.

dashed lines), no significant difference was observed for either radiolabeled DOTATATE ($p = 0.3$) or radiolabelled DOTA-LM3 ($p = 0.7$).

5.4 Discussion

We created realistic virtual models for the adherent CA20948 cell geometry, and thereby obtained significantly different S-values compared to equivalent spherical cell models, with an increase of 13 % (^{177}Lu) and 22 % (^{161}Tb) for the cell membrane and a decrease of 11 % (^{177}Lu) and 12 % (^{161}Tb) for the cytoplasm. However, the impact was lower for the CA20948 cells than for the U2OS cells, for which a decrease of 37 % for the cell membrane and 60 % for the cytoplasm was reported for ^{177}Lu (57). This can be attributed to the more epithelial-like geometry of the U2OS cells, which deviates more from a spherical geometry. Furthermore, assuming a uniform activity distribution and evaluating the absorbed dose to the entire cell had an even larger impact than the cell geometry, and largely overestimated the absorbed dose, especially for the short-range Auger and IC electrons of ^{161}Tb . This assumption of a uniform activity distribution and absorbed dose evaluation is often made at tissue level, and could induce a large overestimation of the absorbed dose, especially when working with short-range radiation types, such as pure or combined Auger emitters like ^{161}Tb , ^{125}I or ^{111}In .

We established absorbed dose-response curves using the more realistic S-values in combination with cell survival and uptake data from previously published dose-response curves (146). The latter one assumed spherical cell models with dimensions estimated using an automated cell counter (Moxi Z, Avantor, Pennsylvania, USA), which overestimated the cellular S-values compared to realistic S-values by 79 % (^{177}Lu) and 98 % (^{161}Tb) for the cell membrane and by 127 % (^{177}Lu) and 159 % (^{161}Tb) for the cytoplasm. As a result, the absorbed dose-response curves were significantly rescaled ($p < 0.0001$) when applying S-values from realistic cellular models, thereby increasing the radiosensitivity parameters that are estimated by fitting a linear or linear-quadratic model to the dose-response curves. However, this difference is mainly attributed to an underestimation of the dimensions of the cell and

Figure 5.3: The clonogenic survival probability of CA20948 cells in function of the absorbed dose by the cell nucleus using realistic cell geometries to model cell nucleus, cytoplasm and cell membrane, including standard deviations. The corresponding fits of the linear and linear-quadratic model are shown with a solid grey line. The dashed line shows the dose-response curves when assuming a spherical cell model with an equivalent volume. The dotted line shows the original dose-response curves from previous literature when assuming a spherical cell model with underestimated dimensions (146).

nucleus ($R_C = 6 \mu\text{m}$ vs. $8.6 \mu\text{m}$ and $R_N = 4 \mu\text{m}$ vs. $5.5 \mu\text{m}$ (146)), since the assumption of a spherical cell model with equivalent volume did not significantly affect the absorbed dose-response curves. Nonetheless, the general conclusions that were drawn from dose-response evaluations remained consistent for both the small spherical and realistic cell geometry models since for both cell models no difference in absorbed dose-response was observed between $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$, and an additional quadratic response for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ was observed compared to $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$.

A limitation of the applied methodology is potential shrinkage of cells after fixation. This might have resulted in a slight overestimation of the calculated S-values. Furthermore, since the S-values are largely dependent on the cell size, the investigated cell type should ideally match the cell dimensions of clinically relevant cells. An even further cellular dosimetry refinement, through the application of microdosimetry, needs a more detailed subcellular localization, such as accumulation of DOTA-TATE in the Golgi apparatus, for example. Moreover, absorbed dose calculations to other radiosensitive targets, such as the cell membrane and mitochondria, will further strengthen our understanding of dose-response relations in

TRT. Nonetheless, we found that the basic spherical cell model is valid for evaluating absorbed dose-response relationships, but that determining the cell dimensions are crucial for accurate cellular dosimetry.

5.5 Conclusion

We developed realistic geometry models for the CA20948 cell type and calculated corresponding S-values for the radioisotopes ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb . These S-values showed substantial intracellular variability and differed significantly from those derived using conventional spherical cell models, however, the use of these realistic S-values did not alter the absorbed dose-response curves when compared to the spherical models. In contrast, when the cell dimensions were underestimated, absorbed dose-response curves were re-scaled, resulting in decreased estimates for the radiobiological parameters α and β that were obtained by fitting a linear quadratic model to the dose response curves. These findings indicate the importance of accurately determining cell dimensions, but support the use of spherical cellular geometries as a valid simplified model for intercomparisons using the same cell line.

Chapter 6

From Uniform to Heterogeneous Dose Models: Connecting Cellular and Tumor Absorbed Dose-Response for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$

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Abstract

In-depth knowledge of tumor absorbed dose–response relationships is a critical first step toward personalizing dose regimens that optimize efficacy while maintaining safety. This study investigated these relationships at a preclinical scale and modeled the observed tumor growth by considering both cellular dose-response relationships and tumor absorbed dose distributions. Using this framework, we compared the tumor dose-response of [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE for peptide receptor radionuclide therapy (PRRT).

Methods CA20948 xenograft-bearing mice were injected with a range of activities of [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE (1 nmol, 21.6 - 115.4 MBq) and [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE (1 nmol, 17.3 - 91.7 MBq). The tumor doubling time was measured and correlated with individual absorbed tumor doses, which were calculated based on quantitative micro-SPECT imaging. In parallel, the tumor dose-response was also modeled based on cellular absorbed dose-response relationships. This analytical tumor-growth-model also considered sub-tumor absorbed dose distributions, which were determined either with digital autoradiography or micro-SPECT.

Results [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE showed a 30 % higher S-value for tumors compared to [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE, after a correction for subcellular heterogeneity. Both treatments reached a clinically relevant tumor absorbed dose-range of 9 - 85 Gy and 5 - 87 Gy (min - max), respectively. A positive correlation was observed between the tumor doubling time and the tumor absorbed dose ($p < 0.0001$, Pearson correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.58$), with no significant difference in tumor absorbed dose-response between [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE ($p = 0.24$). The performance of the analytical tumor-growth-model improved substantially after considering the spatial heterogeneity in absorbed dose within the tumor, with the coefficient of determination increasing from $R^2 = -0.64$ up to $R^2 = 0.16$. The model predicted a plateau in dose-response which was not observed experimentally.

Conclusion The tumor doubling time was found to be positively correlated with the tumor absorbed dose which was largely affected by the heterogeneous dose distribution within the tumor. Findings confirm that [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE does not show an increased therapeutic efficacy compared to [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE.

6.1 Introduction

Evidence data from NETTER-1 phase-3 clinical trial resulted in patients with advanced midgut neuroendocrine tumors (NET) routinely being treated with [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE (14). These evidence data were further complemented with the NETTER-2 study to confirm the efficacy of [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE in earlier lines of treatment (15). While both studies showed a significant increase in progression-free survival, further improvements in therapy efficacy could be considered by personalizing treatments or using other radioisotopes (16).

While the current, approved therapy scheme with [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE uses a standard of 4 cycles with fixed activities of 7.4 GBq, a more individualized treatment plan might avoid both under-treatment and unnecessary toxicities. However, adjusting the injected activity to optimize the lesion and healthy tissue absorbed doses requires standardized dosimetry and reliable dose-response relationships which are currently not well established and therefore not part of the standard of care. Only recently, a limited number of clinical trials did report a positive correlation between the lesion absorbed doses and therapeutic response (8–11). However, this correlation was lacking in another study, potentially due to limitations in the imaging methods (12), which again highlights the difficulties in establishing dose-response relationships. Therefore, further investigation is needed to better understand the absorbed dose-response relationships for targeted radionuclide therapy (TRT), which are required to facilitate personalized treatments.

Next to personalized treatments, dose-response relationships are also valuable for evaluating the use of other radioisotopes such as Terbium-161 instead of Lu-177 to further improve therapy efficacy. Terbium-161 emits additional low energy Auger (11 vs. 1 per decay) and internal conversion (IC; 1.4 vs. 0.15 per decay) electrons compared to ^{177}Lu while it has a similar β^- -spectrum (156 vs. 134 keV / decay) and decays with a similar half-life (6.953 vs. 6.644 d) (4). For [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, these properties have been shown to increase the absorbed dose by 40 % compared to [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE for a tumor of 1 - 10 g (148). Consequently, also an improved preclinical tumor response was observed for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATOC compared to [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATOC for an equal injected activity (23). Nevertheless, an *in vitro* study comparing the clonogenic capacity of [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, did not observe a significantly different dose-response when applying cellular dosimetry, despite the 360 % higher cellular absorbed dose (146). This was devoted to the high linear energy transfer (LET) Auger electrons that did not reach the radiosensitive cell nucleus, and consequently did not increase the biological effectiveness. However, a similar *in vivo* absorbed dose-response comparison between [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, that is clinically much more relevant than the previous *in vitro* comparison, is still lacking.

Peptide Receptor Radionuclide Therapy (PRRT), using either [^{177}Lu]Lu- or [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, could also benefit from PRRT-specific *in vivo* absorbed dose-response models. Like in EBRT, where treatment planning largely relies on mathematical tumor control probability (TCP) models, that describe the probability of complete tumor remission based on the absorbed dose. As described in (2), also PRRT could use such models to assist in both treatment individualization and optimization. One major factor that potentially contributes to variations in absorbed

dose-response, is tumor absorbed dose heterogeneity. This heterogeneous distribution of the absorbed dose over the tumor is mainly due to variable receptor expression levels within the tumor as shown in (45), but also to local variations in tumor perfusion, such that both effects can affect the overall tumor response (43, 96, 149). Accordingly, image-based heterogeneity parameters, such as entropy, were shown to be predictive for tumor response in the NETTER-1 clinical trial (150). Also at a subcellular level, the distribution of activity across the cell compartments will have an impact on the treatment outcome, since the corresponding dose distribution might not always match with the radiosensitive organelles of the cell, which is predominantly the cell nucleus (151). Dose heterogeneity should therefore be considered, at both tissue and subcellular level, when investigating dose-response relations.

Therefore, the aim of this preclinical study was to establish the tumor absorbed dose-response relationships for [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, both experimentally and using an analytical model. The objectives were to 1) get more insight in the dose-response relationship for PRRT, 2) explore the impact of the dose-heterogeneity that is observed on the microscopic level and on the macroscopic tumoral level, and 3) evaluate the therapeutic potential of ¹⁶¹Tb for DOTATATE-based PRRT, as compared to the benchmark ¹⁷⁷Lu.

6.2 Materials & Methods

A more detailed description of the methods can be found in the supplemental materials.

All animal experiments were approved by the local Animal Welfare Committee Animal Studies (NAMSA, Diest), in accordance with Directive 2010/63/EU. Subcutaneous xenografts were established by injecting BalbC nu/nu male mice (Janvier, France) with 5×10^6 CA20948 cells in 200 μ L Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution. Rat pancreatic CA20948 cells were kindly provided by Prof. Nonnekens (Erasmus MC)[16].(135).

6.2.1 Efficacy Study

To assess therapeutic efficacy, 5 treatment groups were defined for both [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE in addition to a control (150 μ l saline) and vehicle (1 nmol cold DOTATATE) group. For each group, 8 mice were injected in the tail vein, two weeks after inoculation, with the injected activities summarized in table 1. The aim was to achieve similar tumor absorbed doses for both [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE of $\sim 20, 40, 60, 80$ and 100 Gy per treatment group. The required injected activity was calculated from the absorbed dose coefficients of $0.8(2)$ Gy/MBq for [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and $1.10(8)$ Gy/MBq for [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE (Pilot study in supplemental materials). The tumor uptake was assumed to be linear as function of the injected activity since the injected peptide amount remained constant (1 nmol), while the molar activity was varied. The radiolabeling of no-carrier-added ¹⁷⁷LuCl (ITM, Germany) and no-carrier-added ¹⁶¹TbCl (SCK CEN, Belgium and TerThera, The Netherlands) to the peptide DOTATATE (ABX, Germany) is described in the supplementary materials.

The tumor volume was measured every other day with a caliper and calculated assuming an ellipsoid:

$$V = \frac{\pi}{6}xyz. \quad (6.1)$$

Mice were euthanized when $V > 2000 \text{ mm}^3$, or when more than 20% weight loss was observed. Mice for which the tumor did not reach $V = 2 \times V_0$, were excluded. The individual relative tumor growth curves were fitted to equation

$$g(t) = a \cdot e^{\lambda \cdot t} + (1 - a) \quad (6.2)$$

with fitting parameters $a \in [0, 1]$ and $0 < \lambda$. This model splits the tumor in an exponential growing and stable fraction. The doubling time for each tumor was then calculated from the inverse function of the fit as $DT = g^{-1}(2)[d]$.

6.2.2 Tumor Dosimetry

For each mouse, the tumor absorbed dose to was calculated as the product of the time-integrated-activity \tilde{A} [Bq s] and the S-value S [Gy / Bq s]. This is equivalent to the product of their normalized analogues \tilde{a} [Bq s / mg] and s [Gy mg / Bq s], which are less dependent on the tumor volume, with convergence when the volume is large compared to the particle range, and noted in lowercase:

$$D = \tilde{A} \cdot S = \frac{\tilde{A}}{V} \cdot (S \cdot V) = \tilde{a} \cdot s. \quad (6.3)$$

6.2.2.1 Time-Integrated-Activity

\tilde{a} was derived from a time-activity profile $f(t)$ [unitless], that reflected the average tracer clearance rate from the tumor lesions. This was determined using longitudinal SPECT scanning of a representative group of mice, injected with a low activity (30 MBq; $n = 4$) or a high activity (90 MBq; $n = 3$) of 1 nmol [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, to verify the independency on the injected activity. The average $f(t)$ was then scaled to the individual tumor uptake a_{2h} [Bq / mg] by performing quantitative SPECT imaging for each mouse at 2 h post injection (p.i.). The tumoral uptake was assumed to be maximal at 2 h p.i. based on a dynamic SPECT study which showed saturation at 1 h p.i. (46). Finally, physical decay with decay constant λ_p was taken into account:

$$\tilde{a} = a_{2h} \cdot \int_0^\infty f(t) \cdot e^{-\lambda_p t} dt \quad (6.4)$$

Details on the longitudinal SPECT imaging and quantitative SPECT imaging can be found in the supplemental materials, together with uncertainty calculations.

6.2.2.2 S-value Simulations for Tumor Absorbed Dose Calculations

S-values were simulated in GATE (147), using the emission spectra (β^- , IC and Auger electrons) from ICRP107 (4), for spherical tumors with a homogeneous activity distribution $s_{T,het}$ and with volumes ranging from a single cell up to 10 mm^3 . These are then linearly interpolated to the investigated tumor volume.

In addition, subcellular heterogeneity of the activity distribution was taken into account to estimate the tumor absorbed dose, since binding of radiolabeled

DOTATATE within the cell is not homogeneous but distributed over the cell membrane (13.6 %) and cytoplasm (86.4 %). Moreover, the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus should be evaluated, since this is the most radiosensitive part of the cell (146). To model this heterogeneity within tumor cells, the single cell s-value $s_{C,hom}$, determined by assuming a spherical cell geometry with a homogeneous activity and dose distribution, was subtracted from the tumor s-value $s_{T,hom}$, and replaced by the heterogeneous single cell s-value $s_{C,het}$ to obtain a tumor S-value that considers subcellular heterogeneity:

$$s_{T,het} = s_{T,hom} - s_{C,hom} + s_{C,het} \quad (6.5)$$

The heterogeneous single-cell S-value $s_{C,het}$ was taken from Spoormans *et al.* ($s_{C,het} = 917 \mu\text{Gy Bq}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{cell}^{-1}$ for ^{161}Tb and $s_{C,het} = 243 \mu\text{Gy Bq}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{cell}^{-1}$ for ^{177}Lu) and multiplied with the cell volume ($V_C = 9.04 \times 10^{-7} \text{mm}^3$), to get the normalized s-value (146). To obtain an estimate for the homogeneous single cell s-value $s_{C,hom}$, the simulated s-value for a spherical tumor with uniform activity distribution was interpolated to the cell volume.

6.2.2.3 Absorbed Dose Uncertainty

The overall uncertainty on the calculated absorbed dose was estimated using standard error propagation rules to consider uncertainties related to estimating the tumoral uptake such as the SPECT calibration, partial volume correction, tumor segmentation and the time activity profile as well as to the S-values. The calibration factor was determined from 9 measurements for ^{177}Lu and 4 measurements for ^{161}Tb , from which the mean and standard deviation were calculated. The standard deviation on the partial volume correction factor was calculated from 5 SPECT vs Gamma counting comparisons for ^{177}Lu and 4 for ^{161}Tb . To provide an average uncertainty for the tumor segmentation, which was assumed to be identical for both $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$, three tumors were segmented independently by 4 different persons. To estimate the uncertainty on the time-activity profile, we generated 10^5 normally distributed random values for the parameters c , λ_1 and λ_2 of equation B.3 based on their best-fit value and standard error from non-linear regression. Subsequently we calculated the corresponding 10^5 time-activity coefficients, from which we could determine the mean and standard deviation. To evaluate the uncertainty on the tumor S-values that was introduced by assuming a spherical geometry for the tumor, the average deviation of the spherical S-values from S-values that used the tumor segmentation as input was calculated. Finally, S-values were randomly simulated while maintaining the Poisson noise below 0.1%.

6.2.3 Tumor Growth Modeling

The *in vivo* absorbed dose-response was modeled using a tumor-growth-model, with as main input the *in vitro* clonogenic cell survival data from a previous study (chapter 5) that followed a linear-exponential absorbed dose-response model

$$S(D) = e^{-\alpha D}, \quad (6.6)$$

with $\alpha = 0.22 \text{Gy}^{-1}$ for both $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$. The tumor-growth-model estimates the relative tumor volume (RTV) over time by partitioning the tumor volume in an active $V_a(D, t)$ and a quiescent $V_q(D, t)$ fraction. The active fraction

consists of all clonogenic cells and grows proportional to the number of clonogenic cells, and thus also to their volume:

$$\frac{dV_a(D, t)}{dt} = \lambda_g \cdot V_a(D, t) \text{ with } V_a(D, 0) = S(D) \cdot V_0 \quad (6.7)$$

with V_0 the total volume at the time of injection. The quiescent fraction consists of all non-clonogenic cells, i.e. $1 - S(D)$, and can shrink due to radiation induced cell death $q(D, t)$:

$$\frac{dV_q(D, t)}{dt} = -q(D, t) \cdot V_q(D, 0) \text{ with } V_q(D, 0) = (1 - S(D)) \cdot V_0. \quad (6.8)$$

An example to model the radiation induced cell death is by assuming both apoptosis and necrosis with a delayed clearance from the tumor T_{cl} :

$$q(D, t) = (q_{ap}(D) + q_{nec}(D)) \cdot \delta(t - T_{cl}) \quad (6.9)$$

however, due to the lack of dose-response data on radiation induced cell death and since the tumor growth curves did not show prominent tumor shrinkage, we had to assume $q(D, t) = 0$. Solving the differential equations yields the following expression for the relative tumor volume, with the absorbed dose evaluated homogeneously over the tumor:

$$RTV_{hom}(D, t) = \frac{V_a(D, t) + V_q(D, t)}{V_0} \quad (6.10)$$

$$= S(D) \cdot e^{\lambda_g \cdot t} + (1 - S(D)). \quad (6.11)$$

The proliferation rate $\lambda_g = 0.08 \text{ d}^{-1}$ was obtained from a fit to the negative control group with $S = 1$.

Up to now, the average tumor absorbed dose D was used, while SPECT and autoradiography images show a largely heterogeneous activity distribution, which is translated in a resulting in a heterogeneous dose distributions due to use of short range radiation types. To account for this absorbed dose heterogeneity within the tumor, the tumor volume was divided in N sub-compartments with volumes V_i each receiving a different uniform absorbed dose D_i and therefore each corresponding to a different $RTV_i(t)$. This results in the following equation for RTV for tumors with a heterogeneous absorbed dose distribution $D_{het} = [D_1, \dots, D_N]$ corresponding to an average absorbed dose D :

$$RTV_{het}(D, t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{V_i}{V} \cdot RTV_i(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{V_i}{V} \cdot [S(D_i) \cdot e^{\lambda_g \cdot t} + (1 - S(D_i)) - q(D_i, t)]. \quad (6.12)$$

The absorbed dose distribution was measured both *ex vivo* using digital autoradiography and *in vivo* using SPECT. *Ex vivo* digital autoradiography (BeaQuant, Ai4R, France) was performed on tumor slices of $n = 4$ mice that were injected with 30 MBq of 1 nmol [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, as described in (149). The measured relative activity distribution was assumed to be independent of the injected activity, since the injected peptide amount remained constant at 1 nmol. Although SPECT images provided the activity distribution at a lower resolution, they offered information on the mouse-specific distribution. Details of both methods are described in detail in the supplementary materials. Finally, the tumor doubling time $DT(D)$ was calculated as:

$$RTV_{hom/het}(D, DT(D)) = 2. \quad (6.13)$$

6.2.4 Statistical Analysis

Group statistics were presented as mean and standard deviation with a p-value ≤ 0.05 considered to be statistically significant. Statistical differences between groups were measured with an unpaired t-test and corrected for multiple testing (scipy.stats.ttest_ind). A two-way ANOVA analysis was used to determine how the administered activities and the choice of radioisotope (^{177}Lu vs ^{161}Tb) affected the tumor doubling time (statsmodels.stats.anova.anova_lm). Curve-fitting was done using non-linear-least-squares-regression (scipy.optimize.curve_fit). X-Y data were compared by evaluating a fitting to a shared curve using the extra sum-of-squares F-test while a positive correlation was evaluated using a sum-of-squares F-test for positive slope. The extend of intra-tumor dose heterogeneity was quantified with a Coefficient of Variance (CoV; std/mean).

6.3 Results

Eleven mice were excluded from the analysis because they did not reach two times their initial tumor volume, from which three mice were not included in the analysis due to excessive weight loss (^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE: groups C and E, ^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE: group D) and 6 mice due to a too large tumor volume at the time of injection (^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE: groups A(2x), C(2x) and D(2x)). For 2 mice, the tumor did shrink to an unmeasurable small size, and did not regrow up to 150 days p.i. (^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE: C and D). As a result, they were considered as complete responders.

6.3.1 Tumor Doubling Times from the *In Vivo* Efficacy Study

The doubling time of the vehicle and control group were not significantly different ($p = 0.5$) and were therefore pooled together as the 'negative control' group (Fig. 6.1, Tab. 6.1). Each treatment group, that was injected with either ^{161}Tb]Tb- or ^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE, showed a significantly higher doubling time compared to the negative control group ($p < 0.001$). The injected activity (A-E; $p < 0.0001$) had a significant effect on the tumor doubling time while the radioisotope had no significant effect ($p = 0.8$).

6.3.2 Tumor Absorbed Doses with a Correction for Subcellular Dose Heterogeneity

The s-values for the IC and Auger electrons were constant over the relevant tumor volume range, while those for the β^- electrons decreased for smaller tumors (Fig. 6.2). For the average tumor volume at the time of injection (*i.e.* 531 mm^3), the β^- electrons had the largest contribution to the total tumor absorbed dose of 80.2% for ^{161}Tb and 90.5% for ^{177}Lu , while the IC and Auger electrons only contributed 19.5% and 0.4% for ^{161}Tb and 9.4% and 0.1% for ^{177}Lu , respectively. The total s-value for ^{161}Tb was found to be 30% higher compared to ^{177}Lu (2.93×10^8 vs. $2.25 \times 10^8 \text{ Gy mm}^3 \text{ Bq}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) while correcting for subcellular had decreased the s-values by 6.5% for ^{161}Tb and by 1.5% for ^{177}Lu .

There was no significant difference between the kinetic profile of the groups with low and high injected activities (extra sum-of-squares F-test, $p = 0.3$) with a shared

Figure 6.1: Tumor growth curves for the different groups together with the median doubling time. ([^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE treated groups A: 20 Gy, B: 33 Gy, C: 44 Gy, D: 63 Gy, E: 66 Gy, [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE treated groups A: 13 Gy, B: 27 Gy, C: 41 Gy, D: 50 Gy, E: 66 Gy, cold DOTATATE treated group (Vehicle) and saline injected group (Control). The markers show the caliper measurements while the curves show the corresponding fit of equation 6.2 to the data points.

Figure 6.2: The s-values for the β^- , IC and Auger electrons for ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb and their total s-value as function of the spherical tumor volume with corresponding radius. The gray area and vertical dashed line represent the respective range ([minimum, maximum]) and average of the tumor volumes at the time of injection. The dotted gray line shows the average volume of a single CA20948 cell.

bi-exponential curve (equation B.3) with fitting parameters $c = 0.33(6)$, $\lambda_1 = 0.63(15) \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $\lambda_2 = 0.064(9) \text{ d}^{-1}$ presenting the best curve-fit (Fig. 6.3). The biological decay that was observed *in vivo* was highly similar to the one determined *in vitro* for up to 7 d (Fig. 6.3, green curve) (146). The tumor uptake and absorbed dose are reported in table 6.1, and plotted against the injected activity (Fig. B.2). The overall uncertainty on the absorbed dose was 13% for ^{177}Lu and 10% for ^{161}Tb , with the largest contributions coming from the time-activity profile, the tumor segmentation and the SPECT calibration factor (Tab. 6.2).

Table 6.1: The mean and standard deviation of the injected activity, tumor uptake 2 h post injection, tumor absorbed dose, doubling time and relative tumor growth delay per treatment group with N is the number of mice included in each group.

Group	Injected activity (MBq)	Tumor uptake (kBq/g)	Absorbed dose (Gy)	Doubling time (d)	Relative tumor growth delay	N
[¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE						
A	21.6(22)	2.3(4)	20(4)	18(7)	0.8(6)	8
B	48.1(24)	3.8(8)	33(7)	31(8)	2.0(8)	8
C	71.4(45)	5.1(11)	44(9)	29(3)	1.8(3)	8
D	87.3(109)	7.3(11)	63(10)	40(6)	2.9(6)	7
E	115.4(63)	7.6(22)	66(19)	54(20)	4.2(19)	9
[¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE						
A	17.3(31)	1.2(3)	13(3)	21(7)	1.0(7)	6
B	36.4(12)	2.3(6)	27(6)	31(7)	2.0(7)	8
C	56.1(20)	3.5(5)	41(5)	40(5)	2.9(5)	4
D	76.7(31)	4.3(7)	50(8)	39(9)	2.8(9)	5
E	91.7(68)	5.7(9)	66(11)	48(12)	3.6(12)	7
Vehicle	-	-	-	10(4)	-	8
Control	-	-	-	9(3)	-	7

Table 6.2: The relative uncertainties of different factors contributing to the overall uncertainty on the tumor absorbed dose calculations. (see section 6.2.2.3 for more details).

	[¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE	[¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE
Uptake at 2 h p.i.	10 %	6 %
<i>SPECT Calibration factor</i>	8 %	3.4 %
<i>Tumor segmentation</i>	5 %	5 %
<i>SPECT vs. GC cross-calibration</i>	2.7 %	2.6 %
Time-activity profile	8 %	8 %
S-value	1.4 %	1.3 %
<i>Assuming spherical tumor geometry</i>	+ 1.4(6) %	+ 1.3(6) %
<i>Poisson noise</i>	< 0.1 %	< 0.1 %
Total	13 %	10 %

The absorbed dose distribution, measured with digital autoradiography for 4 tumors, showed a Coefficient of Variation (CoV) of 38%, 55%, 64% and 87% (Fig. B.1). The absorbed dose distribution did not change when replacing the emission spectrum of ¹⁶¹Tb by the one of ¹⁷⁷Lu, except for tumor B and very low doses which is likely due to the increased Poisson noise in the simulations. Therefore, the heterogeneous tumor-growth-model is not expected to be different between [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu- and [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. The absorbed dose distributions determined from the SPECT images showed an average CoV of 92(42)%, which was not significantly different compared to the CoV observed with autoradiography (t-test, p = 0.15).

6.3.3 Tumor Absorbed Dose-Response Correlations

A positive correlation was observed between the doubling time and the absorbed dose for both [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb- and [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE (slope > 0, p < 0.0001), with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.77 and 0.47 respectively (Fig. 6.4). An extra sum-of-squares F-test did not indicate a significant difference in dose-response for [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb- and [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE (p = 0.24), with a shared linear best-fit of

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.3: a: SPECT/CT images (maximum intensity projection) at 2 h, 1 d, 3 d and 6 d after injection with 90 MBq $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ as part of the longitudinal SPECT study. b: The time-activity profile for $n = 4$ and $n = 3$ tumors after injection of 30 MBq or 90 MBq $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ respectively, decay corrected and normalized to the uptake at 2 h post injection. The corresponding bi-exponential fit (equation B.3) is also shown with corresponding 95 % confidence band, together with the *in vitro* washout profile for $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ in CA20948 cells, as determined in (146).

$DT(D) = a + b \cdot D$ with $a = 13.1(17)$ d and $b = 0.49(4)$ d/Gy and $R^2 = 0.58$. The data did not support the presence of a plateau ($DT(D) = a + b \cdot D/(c + D)$); extra sum-of-squared F-test, $p > 0.05$).

Figure 6.4: Correlation between the tumor doubling time and tumor absorbed dose for mice treated with $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ or $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ together with a negative control group. The individual data points are shown together with the linear regression curve and the 95 % confidence band.

6.3.4 *In Vivo* Validation of the Analytical Tumor-Growth-Models

Both the homogeneous and heterogeneous tumor-growth-models predicted a tumor regrowth after a period of tumor stasis, which was extended by increasing the tumor absorbed dose and which occurred earlier for the heterogeneous model (Fig. 6.5).

The homogeneous tumor-growth-model largely overestimated the experimentally observed doubling times ($R^2 = -64$) while the heterogeneous tumor-growth-model,

Figure 6.5: The modeled tumor-growth curves for different absorbed doses, based on homogeneous (blue) and heterogeneous (orange) absorbed dose distributions, with the dashed line intersecting at the corresponding doubling.

based on the activity distributions from autoradiography data, described the experimental data much better ($R^2 = 0.16$), as shown in figure 6.6. However, a large uncertainty range on the predicted doubling was observed due to intra-tumor variations in the absorbed distributions, with the lowest/highest doubling time predicted from the tumor with the largest/smallest variation in absorbed (CoV = 87% / CoV = 38%, respectively). Since autoradiography data provided relative instead of absolute activity distributions, the model predictions were extrapolated over the whole dose range. This revealed a plateau in the predicted doubling time for the heterogeneous tumor-growth-model, while this was not observed in the experimental data from the efficacy study. Finally, the activity distribution that was measured *in vivo* with SPECT provided the absolute and mouse-specific activity distribution, although at a lower resolution, but did not further improve tumor doubling time predictions ($R^2 = -3$) nor was it able to explain the two complete responders.

6.4 Discussion

The goal of this study was to get more insight in the tumor dose-response relationships for PRRT with [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. Our efficacy study showed a positive correlation between the tumor absorbed dose and doubling time for both [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE with the tumor absorbed dose range (5 - 87 Gy and 9 - 85 Gy (min - max) for [^{177}Lu]Lu- and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, respectively) corresponding to the clinical range of tumor absorbed doses that were reported in GEP-NET lesions after one treatment cycle of 7.4 GBq [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE (1.8 - 98 Gy). This supports recent findings of clinical trials where the tumor absorbed dose was found to be a major predictor of treatment outcome for GEP-NET patients after treatment with [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE (8–11). Meanwhile, the plateau in dose-response, that was described by the EANM radiobiology working group (13), was not observed in our findings. This could be explained by our efficacy study not reaching the range of the cumulative tumor absorbed dose that was reported for the standard 4 treatment cycles (9 - 288 Gy) of PRRT with [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE (8), such that the threshold absorbed dose for reaching a plateau in dose response was possibly not yet achieved.

Figure 6.6: Validation of the homogeneous (blue) and heterogeneous tumor-growth-models against the experimental data for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ (gray). The heterogeneous model based on digital autoradiography (orange) shows the mean and 95% confidence interval and the 4 individual tumors, each with Coefficient of Variation (CoV), all extrapolated over the whole dose-range. The heterogeneous model based on mouse-specific SPECT images (green) are shown at the corresponding homogeneous absorbed dose and highlight the complete responders (red).

However, a direct comparison of our findings with clinically observed dose–response relationships remains challenging. The rapid proliferation of CA20948 cells results in a markedly shortened survival time of inoculated mice, well below three months. This limited survival window precludes the use of the same evaluation time frame as in clinical practice, where treatment response is typically assessed approximately three months after therapy completion. In addition, clinical TCP curves are frequently derived empirically using binary logistic regression of responders versus non-responders, with response categories defined by criteria such as stable (8) or 66% in tumor volume (9). As a result, clinical TCP data are not readily comparable with theoretical TCP models, which by definition estimate the probability that no tumor cell survives treatment. Furthermore, TCP models are suboptimal for PRRT, where heterogeneous dose distribution are expected within the tumor, such that small subregions receiving lower absorbed doses may dominate the overall TCP outcome. This highlights the need for a more appropriate absorbed dose–response modeling approach that includes tumor absorbed dose heterogeneity (152).

Therefore, our study also aimed to investigate the impact of incorporating absorbed dose heterogeneity within a tumor, from microscopic to macroscopic levels, into an analytical tumor growth model based on *in vitro* clonogenic survival data. When assuming a homogeneous dose distribution throughout the tumor, this analytical model largely overestimated tumor doubling time and, consequently, therapeutic efficacy. On the other hand, incorporating absorbed dose heterogeneity resulted in predictions of tumor doubling time that aligned more closely with the experimental observations from our efficacy study. Moreover, this heterogeneous tumor growth model demonstrated a response plateau as described by Pouget et al.

(13), further supporting its validity.

These findings illustrate that the inherently heterogeneous dose deposition of PRRT within tumor lesions substantially diminishes overall tumor response. This was underscored by the predictions of the double time of four tumors with the heterogeneity quantified using autoradiography. For these tumors, the highest predicted doubling time was predicted for the tumor exhibiting the lowest heterogeneity while the lowest double time corresponded to the most heterogeneous tumor. Although the use of SPECT images to assess intratumoral heterogeneity on an individual basis reduced model accuracy, probably because of the inclusion of non-cancerous regions in the tumor segmentation, the heterogeneous model still outperformed the model assuming a homogeneous dose distribution. Importantly, this suggests that SPECT or PET imaging could play a role in the clinical translation of the heterogeneous tumor growth model by enabling the extraction of radiomic features that capture patient-specific tumor heterogeneity.

Nevertheless, despite its improved predictive performance, the heterogeneous model failed to account for the complete responses observed in two mice, indicating the contribution of additional radiobiological processes. Mechanisms such as apoptosis, necrosis, senescence, hypoxia, immune responses, and bystander effects (2, 45, 153) are likely to influence treatment outcomes. A deeper understanding of these processes and their interplay with absorbed dose–response relationships will be essential for further refinement of the model.

Finally, this study also aimed to evaluate the therapeutic potential of ^{161}Tb for PRRT in comparison with the benchmark radioisotope ^{177}Lu . Our findings revealed no significant differences in the tumor absorbed dose–response relationships between ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE and ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE. This is consistent with a recently published *in vitro* study assessing clonogenic survival as a function of absorbed dose to the cell nucleus (146), which found no significant differences between ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE and ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE. More specifically, the study by (146) demonstrated that the high-LET Auger electrons emitted by ^{161}Tb do not reach the radiosensitive cell nucleus when localized in the cytoplasm, and therefore do not enhance the absorbed dose–response for ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE compared to ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE.

In line with these observations, we corrected the *in vivo* tumor absorbed dose for subcellular heterogeneity. This adjustment reduced the absorbed dose for ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE by 6.5 %, highlighting that even at the tumor level, the effects of subcellular dose heterogeneity are non-negligible for short-range emissions. After correction, the relative increase in tumor absorbed dose for ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE compared with ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE was 30 %, as opposed to 40 % when calculated using uniform sphere models (148), and to 360 % at the *in vitro* scale (146).

Despite the equivalent dose–response relationships and the modest increase in absorbed dose when substituting ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE with ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE, ^{161}Tb may still offer therapeutic advantages. In particular, it could be beneficial for the treatment of small metastases, where cross-dose contributions from β^- electrons are minimal, but the multiple low-energy IC electrons from ^{161}Tb can still deliver substantial localized dose to micro-metastatic lesions (Fig. 6.2) ((26, 134, 154, 155)).

Moreover, its potential may be further enhanced if vectors can be optimized for subcellular dose delivery to the nucleus, within the ~ 100 nm range of Auger electrons (156).

6.5 Conclusion

We conducted a preclinical efficacy study in CA20948 xenograft-bearing mice to evaluate tumor response following dose-escalating treatment with [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. Tumor absorbed dose correlated positively with tumor doubling time, supporting absorbed dose as a key determinant of treatment response. However, tumor response was strongly influenced by intratumoral heterogeneity, as demonstrated using an analytical tumor-growth-model based on *in vitro* clonogenic survival data and absorbed dose heterogeneity quantified by digital autoradiography or SPECT. Incorporation of heterogeneity into the model revealed a marked reduction in predicted tumor response. Notably, no significant differences in the absorbed dose–response relationship were observed between [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE.

Chapter 7

Discussion & Conclusion

In this thesis, we investigated TRT-specific absorbed dose-response relationships at a preclinical stage. Cellular clonogenic survival showed clear effects in absorbed dose-response after different PRRT treatments, which allowed to compare the biological effectiveness of different radiopeptides. Complementary, also *in vivo* we studied the tumor absorbed dose-response relationships, which allowed a more clinically relevant evaluation. Both the *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies enabled an extensive comparison of the radioisotopes ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb (section 7.1), and demonstrated the impact of absorbed dose-heterogeneity in TRT (section 7.2). Finally, we were able to predict the *in vivo* tumor doubling time with an analytical model, based on the *in vitro* clonogenic cell survival and *ex vivo* absorbed dose distribution through the tumors (section 7.3).

7.1 Lutetium-177 vs. Terbium-161

Both at cellular and tumor level, we did not observe a significant difference in absorbed dose-response between $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$. The high LET Auger electrons were not able to increase the biological effectiveness since they were not localized near radiosensitive targets, such as the cell nucleus or cell membrane. The latter organelle was targeted by $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ and did induce an additional quadratic component in the cellular absorbed dose-response compared to $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$. However, the absorbed dose-response of $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-LM3}$ was only investigated *in vitro*, up to 6 Gy. An investigation at tumor level could potentially reveal an even larger increase in absorbed dose-response, in case the quadratic trend would continue up to higher and more clinically relevant absorbed doses. Nonetheless, we could conclude that to make benefit of the high LET Auger electrons of ^{161}Tb , subcellular targeting will be crucial.

Literature has already identified multiple targets for auger electrons therapy. Complementary to what we observed in our research, the Montpellier group has investigated the cell membrane as target using the pure Auger electron emitter ^{125}I , and observed an increased radiosensitivity compared to cytoplasmic accumulation, which was devoted to lipid raft formation that moreover mediated a nontargeted response (131, 143, 157). Next, Chan *et al.* were able to localize the pure Auger electron emitter ^{123}I close to the DNA within tumor tissues using a PARP targeting vector, thereby reducing clonogenic capacity, while toxicity to normal tissue was limited due to cytoplasmic accumulation (156). Finally also the mitochondria was identified as a potential target, and dual-targeted ^{161}Tb -radiocomplexes, integrating

PSMA targeting with mitochondrial localization, demonstrated significantly enhanced radiocytotoxicity by increasing DNA damage compared to the single-targeted PSMA complex (151). Together, these studies underscore that precise subcellular delivery, whether to the nucleus, mitochondria, or membrane, can greatly amplify biological impact and optimize the therapeutic potential of Auger electron-based radiopharmaceuticals.

Besides Auger electrons, ^{161}Tb also emits an abundance of IC electrons, about 10 times more compared to ^{177}Lu . S-value calculations showed that in 2D cell cultures, these IC electrons constituted the largest part of the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus for ^{161}Tb -radiolabeled peptides. This induced an increase in absorbed dose to the nucleus of 360 % for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and 380 % for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 compared to their ^{177}Lu -radiolabeled analogues. However, at tumor level, where cells were densely packed, the long-range β^- electrons added a substantial cross-dose for both isotopes. Consequently, the majority of the absorbed dose to the tumor now originated from the β^- electrons, and an increase in absorbed dose of only 30 % was observed for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE compared to [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE. Consequently, for solid tumors, the added value of the isotope ^{161}Tb over ^{177}Lu could be limited when radiolabeled to DOTATATE.

The largest therapeutic potential for ^{161}Tb might be found in the treatment of small metastases. When the size of a lesion drops below the range of the β^- electrons (\sim mm), the cross-dose from the β^- electrons will reduce substantially, while the absorbed dose from short-range IC and Auger electrons will persist. The increase in absorbed dose from [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE compared to [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE will therefore enlarge with decreasing lesion size, as illustrated in figure 6.2 and with the metastatic model of Bernhardt *et al.* (26). Since lesions with a sub-millimeter dimension will be below the detection limit of current imaging methods, an absorbed dose-response investigation at *in vivo* or clinical level will be extremely challenging. 3D *in vitro* models (such as spheroids or tumoroids) could provide a more suitable setting to further investigate the potential of the isotope ^{161}Tb for micrometastases.

Finally, although beyond the scope of this thesis, the absorbed dose to healthy tissues should be considered as well to evaluate the impact on the therapeutic window when replacing [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE by [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. Whole-organ absorbed doses, calculated using Olinda V2.2, showed a similar increase for the kidneys (39 %) and bone marrow (42 %) compared to tumor tissue (40 %) (148). This would mean that the therapeutic window is only minimally affected by the change in radioisotope. However, sub-organ dosimetry of the bone marrow showed a large dependency of the source distribution. Self-irradiation of the radiosensitive active marrow showed an increase of 50 % ($>$ 40 %, negative effect on the therapeutic window), while this was only 15 % - 35 % when the activity was localised in the inactive marrow or the trabecular bone ($<$ 40 %, positive effect on the therapeutic window) (158). Unfortunately, the distribution of DOTATATE within the bone marrow is still unknown, which would be necessary to draw any conclusions regarding the impact on the therapeutic window. Similar sub-organ dosimetry models for other organs at risk, such as the kidney, will be necessary to safely replace [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE by [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE.

7.2 Absorbed Dose Heterogeneity

Absorbed dose heterogeneity had a major impact on absorbed dose-response relationships, both at the cellular and at the tumor level. To begin with, the absence of uptake in the radiosensitive cell nucleus largely reduced the nuclear absorbed dose from the short-range Auger electrons. Consequently, these high LET Auger electrons were not able to increase the absorbed dose-response for [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE compared to [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE. Even though this subcellular absorbed dose distribution is only measurable at a cellular scale, it should be considered at the tumor level as well, since it decreased the tumor absorbed dose by 6.5 % for [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, as found in this study. This is the first subcellular correction performed at a tissue level to our knowledge, and will be especially relevant when evaluating radiopharmaceuticals that employ short-range radiation types.

Besides the radiosensitive cell nucleus, also accumulation at the cell membrane by [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 resulted in a distinct absorbed dose-response curve compared to the internalizing [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. An additional quadratic component was observed when plotting clonogenic survival against absorbed dose, which suggested additional damage at the cell membrane induced by the Auger electrons of ¹⁶¹Tb. This hypothesis demands further research, including both cell membrane dosimetry and membrane integrity assays. The absorbed dose to the cell membrane was not calculated here since this largely depends on the localization of the radioisotopes with respect to the cell membrane, which is of the same dimension as the range of the Auger electrons, *i.e.* nm-scale, and thus below the current resolution of radioactive imaging techniques.

Finally, also at tissue level the absorbed dose-response was largely affected by absorbed dose heterogeneity. The radiopeptides were unevenly distributed throughout the tumor, likely due to variations in receptor expression and perfusion, and since the range of the β^- electrons was still small compared to the tumor size, this resulted in a heterogeneous absorbed dose distribution as well. The absorbed dose distribution was measured both *ex vivo* with digital autoradiography, corrected for cell density, and *in vivo* with SPECT imaging, thereby providing the tumor-specific dose distributions. When including these absorbed dose distributions in the tumor-growth-model, the predictions were drastically improved compared to the homogeneous dose distributions that largely overestimated the experimental tumor doubling times. This indicated how absorbed dose heterogeneity reduced the tumor response, and was in line with previous findings where image-based heterogeneity parameters were found to be predictive for tumor response in the NETTER-1 clinical trial (150). Further research should clarify whether the absorbed dose heterogeneity is stable or fades at later injection cycles. The use of longer range radiation types could limit the absorbed dose-heterogeneity, however, might come with additional healthy tissue toxicities, as was the case for ⁹⁰Y compared to ¹⁷⁷Lu (25). Novel strategies to overcome the problem of absorbed dose heterogeneity could improve TRT treatments significantly, for example additional targeting of the tumor microenvironment, which could correct for a heterogeneous receptor expression, or by employing off-target effects such as immune responses or the bystander effect.

7.3 Absorbed Dose-Response Modeling

Absorbed dose-response models are of large value for treatment planning in EBRT. Clonogenic cell survival is described by the linear-quadratic model, with the linear part characterizing the radiosensitivity of the tissue to the radiation type, the quadratic part representing combined sub-lethal damages, and the α/β -ratio characterizing slow- or fast-proliferating tissue types. This single cell survival is then linked to a macroscopic TCP by multiplying all individual single cell treatment probabilities. The aim in this thesis was to explore similar PRRT-specific absorbed dose-response models at a preclinical level.

For PRRT, except for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3, all investigated radiopeptides better fitted to a linear instead of a linear-quadratic model. This was in line with previous findings (40), and is devoted to the lower dose-rate which enables the repair of sub-lethal damages, and thereby reduces the quadratic component. Additionally, we determined the radiosensitivity parameter $\alpha = 0.22(2) \text{ Gy}^{-1}$ for the CA20948 cells after treatment with either [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE or [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. This was comparable to the radiosensitivity after external ^{137}Cs irradiation of CA20948 cells ($\alpha_{ext} = 0.21(7) \text{ Gy}^{-1}$ (62)), meaning that the effectiveness of β^- or IC particle irradiation is comparable to that of gamma-irradiation. Nonetheless, at higher absorbed doses, external ^{137}Cs irradiation becomes more effective due to the additional quadratic component ($\beta_{ext} = 0.05(2) \text{ Gy}^{-2}$). Finally, for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3, we did observe a quadratic component as well, however, this could not be assigned to the absorbed dose-rate, but might be the result of a synergistic effect of cell membrane and DNA damage. Irradiation induced cell membrane damage has been extensively investigated by the Montpellier group, who described the formation of lipid rafts that activate cellular signaling pathways that lead to DNA damage and cell death (157). These additional delayed DNA damages might contribute to the synergistic effect, however, demand further investigations, for example by evaluating the absorbed dose-response relationships of DOTA-LM3 radiolabeled to a pure Auger emitter, a β^- -emitter and a mixture of both.

To link the cellular absorbed dose-response with macroscopic tumor response in PRRT, the basic TCP model that multiplies all individual treatment probabilities would not be ideal. PRRT is characterized by a heterogeneous absorbed dose distribution, such that the TCP would be completely determined by the lowest absorbed dose regions and approaches zero in most cases, which limits the applicability of the TCP model. Therefore, in this thesis, we proposed an alternative model that describes the tumor growth over time, based on *in vitro* clonogenic data. The model predicted a tumor stasis followed by a tumor regrowth, with the tumor-growth-delay extending with increasing absorbed doses. This matched with the experimentally observed tumor growth curves. While the model, based on homogeneous tumor dose, largely overestimated the tumor doubling time, the predictions improved substantially after a correction for absorbed dose heterogeneity, using either SPECT or autoradiography. This demonstrated how absorbed dose-heterogeneity in PRRT reduces the treatment efficacy, as discussed in section 7.2.

To our knowledge, this was the first PRRT-specific absorbed dose-response model that was validated against experimental data. Even though the model is relatively simple, it was able to predict the tumor doubling time relatively well, albeit with a large

variability, which was inherent to the variation in absorbed dose heterogeneity. To further improve the model, more radiobiological aspects should be included, such as apoptosis or necrosis, which would reduce the tumor volume, hypoxia, which might radiosensitize regions with low perfusion, or senescence, which might cause a tumor stasis. This would require more information on their absorbed dose-response relationships, however, might give a better understanding on their impact on tumor response. Also off-target effects such as immune responses and bystander effects contribute to tumor response in PRRT and should be integrated in the model (157, 159). Furthermore, the use of an [^{18}F]Fluorodeoxyglucose(FDG)-PET scan might improve the model as well, by identifying the active tumoral tissue regions and excluding for example a necrotic core. Moreover, the model should also be adapted to the multiple treatment cycles that are applied clinically. At this moment, the main application for the model should be radiopharmaceutical development (for example: choice of novel vector and radioisotopes) and TRT basic research. Ideally, after further development and validation it could assist during treatment planning at a clinical level as well.

7.4 Limitations & Future Directions

One major limitation of this study was the restricted dose range used to establish the cellular dose–response curves. This limitation was more pronounced for ^{177}Lu than for ^{161}Tb , complicating direct comparisons between the isotopes. Consequently, the limited range may have obscured a potentially larger difference in dose–response between [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3, particularly if the quadratic component of the response persists at higher doses. This could be clarified by extending the analysis to include tumor-level dose–response evaluations.

Expanding the *in vitro* absorbed dose range would require an increase in molar activity, since receptor saturation was already reached at higher activity concentrations. Further increases would only enhance the contribution of non-specific absorbed dose from the culture medium. Alternatively, the medium’s absorbed dose could be exploited to approximate the cross-dose observed within a solid tumor, although this approach would require careful adjustment of activity concentration and exposure duration. A more robust solution would be the implementation of 3D *in vitro* models, such as spheroids or tumoroids, which better represent the spatial dose distribution and absorption characteristics of clinical tumors while maintaining experimental control.

Although absorbed dose distributions were successfully measured in tumors both *in vivo* and *ex vivo*, the assessment of heterogeneity effects relied on modeling assumptions. Given the substantial estimated impact of this heterogeneity, further experimental validation is warranted. One promising direction would be a voxel-wise correlation between absorbed dose and radiobiological markers such as SSTR2 expression or perfusion, which could help elucidate the sources of heterogeneity. Similarly, correlating absorbed dose with biological endpoints such as apoptosis, necrosis, proliferation rate, DNA damage, and senescence could provide deeper insight into the biological consequences of dose heterogeneity. Furthermore, non-targeted effects—including bystander effects and immune responses—should be examined, as these mechanisms may mitigate or amplify the impact of dose

heterogeneity, as previously demonstrated in GRID therapy for EBRT (127).

Finally, integrating such correlations into the tumor growth model could enhance its predictive accuracy. Once further validated, this model could serve as a tool to explore different treatment regimens and optimize therapeutic strategies. In this context, a more comprehensive understanding of how factors such as SSTR2 expression, radiosensitivity, and absorbed dose heterogeneity evolve across multiple treatment cycles would be of considerable value.

7.5 Conclusions

The goal of this thesis was to explore absorbed dose-response relationships for PRRT at a preclinical level. Since dosimetry in TRT is rather complex, absorbed dose-response relationships are only rarely established, and often involve many assumptions. Nonetheless, they reveal the underlying radiobiological responses, and in this thesis allowed a profound evaluation of PRRT-specific irradiation characteristics and novel radiopharmaceuticals.

Cellular absorbed dose-response relationships learned us how the internalisation of DOTATATE hampered the increase in biological effectiveness of [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE over [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE. The efficacy of the short-range Auger electrons was largely dependent on the subcellular distribution, meaning that subcellular targeting of radiosensitive organelles will be crucial to fully exploit their high LET. Furthermore, detailed absorbed dose-calculations revealed how the relative contribution of the additional IC electrons of ¹⁶¹Tb increased with decreasing dimensions. Consequently, the additional absorbed dose for [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE over [¹⁷⁷Lu]Lu-DOTATATE was only 30 % for solid tumors, while it reached up to 360 % at cellular level, which highlights a large advantage for small micro-metastases. Finally, we were able to link the cellular and tumor absorbed dose-response relationships using an analytical tumor growth model. The validation of the model against experimentally observed tumor doubling times showed a significant improvement of the predictions when including absorbed dose distributions from either autoradiography or SPECT images. This illustrated the extensive impact of absorbed dose-heterogeneity on PRRT treatment efficacy.

None of the above conclusions could have been drawn by only considering the administered activity. This points out the relevance of dosimetry in preclinical evaluations, which is at the moment often omitted. Both the methodologies for the *in vitro* and *in vivo* established absorbed dose-response curves could serve as an example for further research. However, in addition, alternatives such as 3D cell cultures should be considered as well, since they represent a more relevant absorbed dose distribution, while being relatively accessible and controllable. Finally, while this thesis presented an extensive investigation of tumor absorbed dose-response relationships, they should eventually be evaluated next to healthy tissue absorbed dose-response relations, since the final goal is to safely increase the efficacy of PRRT treatments, and to expand the therapeutic window.

Scientific Acknowledgments and Personal Contribution

The full manuscript was drafted by Kaat Spoormans and was proofread by Michel Koole, Melissa Crabbé and Lara Struelens. Chapter 2 was also proofread by the co-author Marijke De Saint-Hubert and chapter 4 by the co-authors Koen Vermeulen and Marijke De Saint-Hubert.

The outline of the PhD research was drafted by the supervisors Melissa Crabbé, Lara Struelens and Michel Koole, and further refined by Kaat Spoormans. The S-value simulations, absorbed dose calculations, tumor growth modeling, experimental design, experimental work, analysis and interpretation of result were all done by Kaat Spoormans, except for some assistance listed below:

- Assistance in optimisation of radiolabelling protocols:
Tomas Opsomer and Koen Vermeulen
- Optimisation of cell culture, seeding densities and uptake protocol:
Lorain Geenen
- Assistance in uptake experiments:
Melissa Crabbé, Amelie Coolkens, Michelle Andersson
- Optimisation SPECT reconstruction protocols:
Melissa Crabbé and Sunay Rodriguez Pérez
- Calibration of quantitative equipment:
A joint effort of Kaat Spoormans, Michelle Andersson, Sunay Rodriguez Pérez, Clarita Saldarriaga Vargas and Melissa Crabbé
- Assistance in tumor inoculations:
Melissa Crabbé, Charlotte Segers, Amelie Coolkens
- IV injections of Radiopharmaceuticals:
Mieke Neefs, Jasmien Wellens, Melissa Crabbé and Koen Vermeulen
- Daily follow-up of mice and bi-daily tumor measurements:
Animal care-takers Lisa Daenen and Sandy Cools

Conflict of Interests

This PhD research was fully funded by the Belgian nuclear research center SCK CEN and Melissa Crabbé and Lara Struelens are employed at this institution.

The use of Generative AI

Generative AI was merely used to improve the grammar of chapter 4 and to segment all cell nuclei in the H&E images of chapter 6 using the AI software Biodock (US).

Curriculum Vitae

Education

- **M.Sc in Physics**
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University of Antwerp — Sept 2015 - June 2016

List of Publications

Published

- **Spoormans, K.**, Crabbé, M., Struelens, L., Saint-Hubert, M. D., and Koole, M. (2022). A Review on Tumor Control Probability (TCP) and Preclinical Dosimetry in Targeted Radionuclide Therapy (TRT). *Pharmaceutics* 14, DOI: 10.3390/pharmaceutics14102007
- Bolcaen, J., Combrink, N., **Spoormans, K.**, *et al.* (2023). Biodosimetry, can it find its way to the nuclear medicine clinic? *Front Nucl Med* 3. DOI: 10.3389/fnume.2023.1209823
- **Spoormans, K.**, Struelens, L., Vermeulen, K., de Saint-Hubert, M., Koole, M., Crabbé, M. (2024). The Emission of Internal Conversion Electrons Rather Than Auger Electrons Increased the Nucleus-Absorbed Dose for ^{161}Tb Compared with ^{177}Lu with a Higher Dose Response for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTA-LM3 Than for [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. *J Nucl Med* 65, DOI: 10.2967/JNUMED.124.267873
— Alavi-Mandell award

Submitted

- **Spoormans, K.**, Crabbé, M., Struelens, L., M., Koole, M. Realistic versus Spherical Cellular Geometry Models: Impact on Dose–Response of CA20948 Cells to ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb -Labeled DOTATATE and DOTA-LM3.
Submitted as a short communication to the European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging - Physics.
- **Spoormans, K.**, Crabbé, M., Struelens, L., M., Koole, M. From Uniform to Heterogeneous Dose Models: Connecting Cellular and Tumor Absorbed Dose-Response for [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE
Submitted to the European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging.

In preparation

- Metha, A., **Spoormans, K.**, *et al.* Absorbed dose-response relationships for ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb -labeled radiopeptides.
In scope of a research collaboration with the Center for Radiopharmaceutical Sciences ETH-PSI-USZ, Paul Scherrer Institute, 5232 Villigen, Switzerland.
- **Spoormans, K.**, *et al.* A preclinical evaluation of the radiopeptides ^{135}La -DOTATATE and ^{135}La -DOTA-LM3.

Presentations

- *Internal Conversion electrons are the main contributors of the increased nuclear absorbed dose of ^{161}Tb - versus ^{177}Lu -DOTATATE*
Oral presentation — Auger symposium — Montpellier, France — 09 Sep 2023
— Best presentation award
- *The dose-response effects of the additional Auger and IC electrons of ^{161}Tb - compared to ^{177}Lu -labelled agonists and antagonists*
Oral presentation — EANM congress — Hamburg, Germany — 19 Oct 2024 —
Highlighted presentation
- *The impact of absorbed dose heterogeneity on ^{161}Tb -DOTATATE treatment*
Oral presentation — IWRMR — Rotterdam, The Netherlands — 07 Apr 2025

Experience

- *Research visit in scope of a collaboration on cellular dosimetry*
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Appendix A

Supplemental Materials of Chapter 4

A.1 Saturation Binding

A saturation binding experiment was conducted to determine the total amount of bound radioligand per cell as a function of administered activity concentration. Cells were treated with both ^{177}Lu - and ^{161}Tb -labelled DOTATATE or DOTA-LM3 (1/2 dilution series from 5 MBq/mL up to 0.01 MBq/mL). The stock solution to prepare the dilution series was measured in an eppendorf with the Isomed 2010 dose calibrator (Nuvia Instruments, France), which was calibrated to a secondary standard radionuclide calibrator (Fidelis, National Physics Laboratory, Teddington, United Kingdom). To determine non-specific binding, cells were incubated with a blocking solution containing cold DOTA-TATE or DOTA-LM3 (5 μM) prior to the treatment. After 4 hours of incubation, the treatment was removed, and the cells were washed twice with ice-cold phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.45). The cell membrane bound fractions were collected after 10 minutes incubation with ice-cold stripping buffer (50 mM glycine in 100 mM NaCl, pH 2.8) and two washing steps with PBS. Next, cells were incubated for 30 minutes with ice-cold lysis buffer (1 M NaOH), washed twice with ice-cold PBS and collected as the internalized fractions. The collected cell fractions were measured with an automated gamma counter (2480 wizard2, Perkin Elmer, Zaventem, Belgium), and normalized to the average number of cells per well, which was measured in one well of each of the three replicate plates. The conversion of counts per minute (CPM) to activity (Bq) was done based on a calibration curve derived from a dilution series of which the original activity was measured in a secondary standard radionuclide calibrator (Fidelis, National Physics Laboratory, Teddington, United Kingdom). The activity per cell was converted to fmol/cell after division with Am. The administered activity from which the Am was calculated was measured with a dose calibration (type). The results were fitted to the one site total and non-specific binding model of GraphPad (Prism, GraphPad, Massachusetts, USA)

$$B_{4h}(a) = \frac{B_{max} \cdot a}{K_d + a} + NS \cdot a \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where B_{4h} is the number of bound radiopharmaceuticals per cell after 4 hours, a is the added activity concentration and B_{max} , K_d and NS are fitting parameters representing the maximal specific binding, affinity, and non-specific binding, respectively.

A.2 Uptake Kinetics

Association kinetics were determined for ^{161}Tb -labelled peptides and the dissociation kinetics were determined for ^{177}Lu , with the assumption that the kinetics of the radiopeptides are independent of the radioisotope (see the results section and previously published data)(14). For the association kinetics, the cells were treated with a low (2.4 kBq/mL), medium (78 kBq/mL) and high (1250 kBq/mL) activity concentration since the association rate is expected to be dependent on the concentration (15). The added activity was removed at different time points (15, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180, 210 and 240 minutes), after which the cell fractions were collected.

One concentration (100 kBq/mL) was used for the dissociation kinetics since these kinetics are expected to be independent of the added activity concentration (15). After 4 hours, the activity was removed, cells were washed twice with PBS and fresh culture medium was added. At later time points (1 - 7 days), the medium was removed, and cells were washed twice with ice-cold PBS, which was collected to estimate the unbound fraction. Next, the cell membrane fraction was removed as described above and subsequently measured. To account for any activity that adhered to the well plate over time, the cells were trypsinized and centrifuged, after which the supernatant was removed, and the cell pellet was dissolved in PBS and measured as the internalized fraction. The measured samples were normalized to the total activity measured in the well (unbound, cell membrane and internalized fraction), to present the result as a fraction of the total cell binding at 4 h. Combining this kinetic information with the saturation binding data provided the bound radiopeptides per colony over time. The data were corrected by the number of cells per colony over time, to correct for cell division, under the assumption that the activity was evenly distributed over the daughter cells. The number of colonies followed an exponential increase $e^{\ln(2) \cdot t / T_d}$ (2) with doubling time T_d , which was measured by longitudinal imaging of the colony formation.

A.3 TIAC Calculation

The results of the saturation binding assay fitted to the following equation,

$$B_{4h}(a) = \frac{B_{max} \cdot a}{K_d + a} + NS \cdot a \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where B_{4h} is the number of bound radiopharmaceuticals per cell after 4 hours, a is the added activity concentration and B_{max} , K_d and NS are fitting parameters. The association kinetics during the 4 hours of incubation followed equation

$$B(t < 4h) = C \cdot (1 - \exp(-k_a(a) \cdot t)) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

with t the time, C a fitting constant and

$$k_a(a) = k_{off} + k_{on} \cdot a \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The parameters k_{off} and k_{on} are derived from a linear fit through the three $k_a(a)$ values obtained from the low, medium and high activity concentration. The kinetic parameters

Figure A.1: The time-activity-curves of 1.25 MBq/mL $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTA-TATE}$. The blue curve represents the activity per cell due to solely ligand uptake, excretion and cell death. The orange curve also considers physical decay while the green curve also accounts for cell division, which is used for dosimetry. The error bands correspond to ± 1 standard deviation

$k_a(a)$ where combined with the total uptake at 4 h from the saturation binding to obtain the time activity curve for $t < 4h$:

$$A(a, t) = \frac{1 - \exp(-k_a \cdot t)}{1 - \exp(-4k_a)} \cdot B_{4h}(a) \cdot M \cdot \exp(-\lambda_p t) \quad \text{for } t < 4h \quad (\text{A.5})$$

together with the molar activity M and the physical decay constant λ_p . This total activity per cell was multiplied with the internalisation fraction f_{int} to get the activity in the cytoplasm, or with $(1 - f_{int})$ to get the membrane bound activity. f_{int} was determined within both the saturation binding and the association assay.

During the dissociation phase ($t > 4h$), f_{int} varied over time and a different behaviour for DOTA-TATE and DOTA-LM3 was observed, which required different fits. The cell membrane fraction of DOTA-TATE was constant over time,

$$F_{DOTATATE_{CM}}(4h < t) = 1 - f_{int} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

while the internalized fraction followed an exponential decay

$$F_{DOTATATE_{int}}(4h < t) = (f_{int} - P_{int}) \cdot \exp(-K_{int} \cdot (t - 4h)) + P_{int} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

The DOTA-LM3 peptide had an exponentially decaying cell membrane fraction

$$F_{DOTA-LM3_{CM}}(4h < t) = (1 - f_{int} - P_{CM}) \cdot \exp(-K_{CM} \cdot (t - 4h)) + P_{CM}. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

which began to internalize over time. As a result, the internalized fraction followed an initial increase, after which it began to increase. This behaviour fitted the following model

$$F_{DOTA-LM3_{int}}(4h < t) = C_{int} \cdot (1 - \exp(-K_{CM} \cdot t)) \cdot \exp(-K_{int} \cdot t). \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Within the dissociation assay, the uptake F was measured as a fraction of the bound activity per cell at 4 hour, such that the activity curves for $t > 4h$ are given by

$$A(a, t) = B_{4h}(a) \cdot \frac{F_{CM}(t) + F_{int}(t)}{N_{colony}(t)} \cdot M \cdot \frac{\exp(-\lambda_p t)}{R} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

for both peptides. The number of cells per colony $N_{colony}(t)$ accounts for the reduced activity due to cell division.

Table A.1: Fitting parameters of the models for the uptake assays

assay	model [†]	parameter	DOTA-LM3 [‡]	e+ [§]	DOTA-TATE [‡]
Saturation binding	S1	B_{max} (10^3 fmol/cell)	0.78 ± 0.14	*	1.14 ± 0.34
	S1	K_d (nM)	0.61 ± 0.05	**	0.97 ± 0.42
	S1	NS (10^6 fmol/cell/nM)	2.7 ± 1.3	ns	1.9 ± 1.4
Association	S3	k_{on} (h^{-1} nM ⁻¹)	0.014 ± 0.016	ns	0.160 ± 0.109
	S3	k_{off} (h^{-1})	0.83 ± 0.18	ns	0.24 ± 0.13
Internalization	f_{int}		$10.5\% \pm 0.8\%$	****	$86.4\% \pm 6.2\%$
Dissociation	S6	k_{int} (d ⁻¹)	/		0.23 ± 0.02
	S6	P_{int}	/		$20\% \pm 4\%$
	S7	K_{CM} (d ⁻¹)	0.671 ± 0.019		/
	S7	P_{CM}	$16.4\% \pm 0.5\%$		/
	S8	C_{int}	$74.1\% \pm 1.9\%$		/
	S8	k_{int} (d ⁻¹)	0.098 ± 0.006		/

*There was no significant difference for the saturation binding fitting parameters of the ¹⁶¹Tb- and ¹⁷⁷Lu-labelled peptides, so these data were pooled together.

+ unpaired t-test; alpha = 0.05, ns = not significant, * p ≤ 0.05, ** p ≤ 0.01, **** p ≤ 0.0001

‡models are summarized in the SUPPLEMENTAL materials

Next, these time activity curves were numerically integrated over time to obtain the TIAC per cell $\tilde{A}_{cell}(a)$. For the cross-dose, a distinction needed to be made between the incubation phase ($t \leq 4$ h), with a high uniform cell density, and the colony forming phase ($t > 4$ h), with a few cells, closely packed in colonies that grow over time. The corresponding TIAC's per cell are therefore given by

$$\tilde{A}_{inc.}(a) = \int_0^{4h} A(a, t) dt \quad (A.11)$$

$$\tilde{A}_{colony}(a) = \int_{4h}^{\infty} A(a, t) dt \quad (A.12)$$

$$(A.13)$$

Finally, also the TIAC of the culture medium has to be divided in the incubation and colony forming phase. During the incubation phase, this equals all the added activity minus the activity taken up by the N cells

$$\tilde{A}_{med.,inc.}(a) = \int_0^{4h} (a \cdot 1ml \cdot \exp(-\lambda_p t) - N \cdot A(t, a)) dt, \quad (A.14)$$

while during the colony forming phase, there is only the activity excreted by the cells

$$\tilde{A}_{med,colony}(a) = \int_{4h}^{\infty} N \cdot B_{4h}(a) \cdot (A - F_{CM}(t) - F_{int}(t)) \cdot M \cdot \exp(-\lambda_p t) dt \quad (A.15)$$

A.4 S-Value Simulations

The average absorbed doses to the nucleus per nuclear decay, which are the S-values, were estimated with the Monte Carlo particle transportation code Geant4

version 11.0.1. ((138–140)). The physics list G4EmStandardPhysics_option4 was used with a production cut of 0.01 μm . As input data, the continuous β^- and discrete IC and Auger spectra were taken from the ICRP107 database ((4))(Fig.A.2), while X-rays and photons were neglected ((141)). Sufficient primary particles were generated to obtain a root-mean-square error below 1 %.

Figure A.2: The emission spectra of the beta, IC and Auger electrons for ^{161}Tb and ^{177}Lu from ICRP107 database ((4)). Note the different energy scales.

Cells and nuclei were assumed to be concentric water spheres. The cell radius (6 μm) was calculated by the automated cell counter (Moxi Z, Avantor, Pennsylvania, USA) while the radius of the nuclei was extracted from microscopy images (BioTek Cytation, Agilent, California, USA) with a DAPI staining (4 μm). For S_{medium} a single cell was placed in a central position in the well, particle emissions were uniformly placed throughout the well and the dose was scored in the nucleus. For S_{cross} cells were placed at various inter-cell distances from each other, particle emissions were distributed within one cell while the dose was scored in the nuclei of the other cells. A linear interpolation of the corresponding S-values was then used to calculate the average S-value of a uniform cell distribution in a 12-well plate. This S_{cross} corresponded to the cross-dose during the first 4 hours of incubation, while after these 4 hours the cross-dose originated from cells within the colony, S_{colony} . The colony was represented as a flat cylinder, with the height equal to the cell diameter and the cross area corresponding to the average colony area at each day. The latter was extracted from live cell imaging of the growing colonies over time. Finally, the self-dose S-values were calculated by distributing the activity on either the outer surface (cell membrane: S_{CM}) of the cell or in between the cell surface and the nucleus (cytoplasm: S_{cyto}).

Table A.2: S-values per radioisotope and type of particle emission

$(\mu\text{Gy/Bq s}^{-1})$		β^-	IC	Auger
$S_{CM-nucleus}$	^{161}Tb	190.2	720.4	6.882
	^{177}Lu	211.1	31.3	0.8735
$S_{\text{Cyto-nucleus}}$	^{161}Tb	297.2	1222	128
	^{177}Lu	338.6	47.72	20.76
$S_{\text{Cross-nucleus}}$ (per cell)	^{161}Tb	$(352 \pm 112)\text{E-6}$	$(243 \pm 239)\text{E-6}$	$(5 \pm 5)\text{E-6}$
	^{177}Lu	$(335 \pm 120)\text{E-6}$	$(63 \pm 28)\text{E-6}$	$(1.1 \pm 0.9)\text{E-6}$
day 0	^{161}Tb	33 ± 4	84 ± 10	1.27 ± 0.16
	^{177}Lu	32 ± 3	7.2 ± 0.7	0.26 ± 0.04
day 1	^{161}Tb	26.0 ± 0.8	58 ± 3	0.97 ± 0.05
	^{177}Lu	28.3 ± 0.8	5.9 ± 0.3	0.18 ± 0.03
day 2	^{161}Tb	10 ± 2	21 ± 5	0.49 ± 0.09
	^{177}Lu	11 ± 2	2.4 ± 0.5	0.06 ± 0.03
day 3	^{161}Tb	4.9 ± 1.1	9.3 ± 1.9	0.21 ± 0.11
	^{177}Lu	5.2 ± 1.2	0.9 ± 0.2	0.028 ± 0.012
day 4	^{161}Tb	2.8 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 0.4	0.03 ± 0.03
	^{177}Lu	1.6 ± 0.2	2.6 ± 0.4	0.04 ± 0.04
day 5	^{161}Tb	1.38 ± 0.12	1.98 ± 0.14	0.041 ± 0.004
	^{177}Lu	1.19 ± 0.12	1.88 ± 0.14	0.040 ± 0.003
day 6	^{161}Tb	0.98 ± 0.12	0.92 ± 0.13	0.010 ± 0.005
	^{177}Lu	0.90 ± 0.11	0.70 ± 0.13	0.010 ± 0.005
day 7	^{161}Tb	0.99 ± 0.12	0.21 ± 0.03	0.006 ± 0.006
	^{177}Lu	0.99 ± 0.12	0.21 ± 0.03	0.006 ± 0.006
$S_{\text{Medium-nucleus}}$	^{161}Tb	$(141 \pm 0.4)\text{E-6}$	$(1.71 \pm 0.13)\text{E-6}$	$(48 \pm 7)\text{E-9}$
	^{177}Lu	$(11.9 \pm 0.4)\text{E-6}$	$(163 \pm 11)\text{E-9}$	$(8.5 \pm 0.9)\text{E-9}$

The errors correspond to the natural inter-cell variation of the S-values.
IC = Internal Conversion

Appendix B

Supplemental Materials of Chapter 6

B.1 Detailed Materials & Methods

B.1.1 Radiolabelling

No-carrier-added $^{177}\text{LuCl}$ (ITM, Germany) and no-carrier-added $^{161}\text{TbCl}$ (SCK CEN, Belgium and TerThera, The Netherlands) were radiolabeled to the peptide DOTATATE (ABX, Germany) at 95 °C for 15 min or 10 min, respectively. Radiolabeling was done in 0.25 M NaOAC (pH 4.7) and 40 mM ascorbic acid, with 1 nmol DOTATATE per 100 μL radiolabeled to 24 MBq (A), 48 MBq (B), 72 MBq (C), 96 MBq (D) or 120 MBq (E) $^{177}\text{LuCl}$ or 18 MBq (A), 36 MBq (B), 55 MBq (C), 73 MBq (D) or 91 MBq (E) $^{161}\text{TbCl}$. One-hundred μL of the radiolabeling solution was diluted with 50 μL physiological saline before injection. The radiochemical purity and conversion was checked with instant thin-layer chromatography after each radiolabeling (> 99%). The radiolytic stability was verified by high-performance liquid chromatography (> 97% up to 6 h).

B.1.2 Radiopeptide Injections

To assess therapeutic efficacy, 5 treatment groups were defined for both ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE and ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE in addition to a control and vehicle group. For the treatment groups, the aim was to achieve similar tumor absorbed doses of 20 Gy, 40 Gy, 60 Gy, 80 Gy and 100 Gy per treatment group for both ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE and ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE. The required injected activity was determined based on absorbed dose coefficients determined in a pilot experiment where $n = 4$ mice were injected with 1 nmol (30 MBq) ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE. This resulted in a tumor uptake of 3.1(7) MBq/g at 2 h p.i, and combined with the longitudinal SPECT study, described in the next section, and S-values that were simulated assuming spherical tumors ($2.25 \times 10^8 \text{ Gy mg Bq}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $3.09 \times 10^8 \text{ Gy mg Bq}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb , respectively), this provided the absorbed dose coefficients of 0.8(2) Gy/MBq for ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE and 1.10(8) Gy/MBq for ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE. The tumor uptake was assumed to be linear as function of the injected activity since the injected peptide amount remained constant (1 nmol), while the molar activity was varied. Therefore, for each treatment group, 8 mice were injected in the tail vein two weeks after inoculation with 1 nmol ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE (A: 22(2) MBq, B: 48(2) MBq, C: 71(4) MBq, D: 87(11) MBq, E: 115(6) MBq), 1 nmol ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE (A: 17(3) MBq, B: 36.4(12) MBq, C: 56(2) MBq, D: 77(3) MBq, E: 92(7) MBq), 1 nmol cold DOTATATE (vehicle) or 150 μL saline (control). The syringes were measured before and after each injection with a radionuclide calibrator (VIK202,

Comecer), which was calibrated to a secondary standard (FIDELIS, NPL, United Kingdom) for both ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb , to ensure the actual injected activity is measured.

B.1.3 Tumor Dosimetry

The absorbed dose to the tumor tissue was calculated for each mouse individually as the product of the time-integrated-activity \tilde{A} [Bq s] and the S-value S [Gy / Bq s]. This is equivalent to the product of their normalized analogues \tilde{a} [Bq s / mg] and s [Gy mg / Bq s], which are less dependent on the tumor volume, with convergence when the volume is large compared to the particle range, and which will be used later on:

$$D = \tilde{A} \cdot S = \frac{\tilde{A}}{V} \cdot (S \cdot V) = \tilde{a} \cdot s. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

The time-integrated activity coefficient \tilde{a} was determined by using an averaged decay-corrected time-activity curve $f(t)$ [unitless], that reflected the average tracer clearance rate from the tumor lesions and that was determined using longitudinal SPECT scanning (section B.1.3.3). The average $f(t)$ was then scaled to the individual tumor uptake by performing quantitative SPECT imaging (section B.1.3.2) individually for each mouse at 2 h post injection (p.i.) to determine a_{2h} [Bq / mg]. Two hours p.i. was chosen as time point for imaging because at this time point maximal tumoral uptake can be assumed based on a dynamic SPECT study by O'Neill *et al.* which showed saturation at 1 h p.i. (46). Finally, physical decay with decay constant λ_p was taken into account to calculate \tilde{a} from the image-based estimate for a_{2h}

$$\tilde{a} = a_{2h} \cdot \int_0^{\infty} f(t) \cdot e^{-\lambda_p t} dt \quad (\text{B.2})$$

B.1.3.1 Pilot Study for the Absorbed Dose Coefficients

A pilot study was conducted to estimate the absorbed dose coefficients for CA20948 tumors after [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE or [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE treatment. This allowed to determine the required injected activities to reach an optimal absorbed dose range that is close to the clinical absorbed doses and that is consistent for both radioisotopes.

In this pilot study, $n = 4$ mice were injected with 1 nmol (30 MBq) [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, which resulted in a tumor uptake of 3.1(7) MBq/g at 2 h p.i. . The full time-activity curve was established with a longitudinal SPECT study (see section B.1.3.3) and S-values were simulated assuming spherical tumors (2.25×10^{-8} Gy mg Bq $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$ and 3.09×10^{-8} Gy mg Bq $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$ for ^{177}Lu and ^{161}Tb , respectively).

Absorbed dose coefficients of 0.8(2) Gy/MBq and 1.10(8) Gy/MBq were found for [^{177}Lu]Lu-DOTATATE and [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, respectively.

B.1.3.2 Quantitative SPECT Imaging

A MILabs High-Energy U-SPECT⁶CT^{HR} (v2020) system was used together with the HE-GP-M multi-pinhole collimator with \varnothing 1.4 mm pinholes. The field-of-view was centered around the tumor, and the scan time was adapted to the injected activity of the group (A: 60 min, B: 30 min, C: 20 min, D: 15 min and E: 12 min). Images were

reconstructed with SROSEM (4 iterations) using double energy windows $114 \text{ keV} \pm 7 \%$ and $203 \text{ keV} \pm 6 \%$ for ^{177}Lu and $52 \text{ keV} \pm 5 \%$ combined with $78 \text{ keV} \pm 7.5 \%$ for ^{161}Tb with a voxel size of 0.4 mm. CT-based attenuation correction was performed. Tumors were segmented manually based on the CT image, and the average count-rate over the tumor volume was evaluated. This was converted to the average activity concentration in the tumor a_{2h} by applying a calibration factor, which was extracted from phantom scans that contained an activity traceable to a secondary standard radionuclide calibrator (FIDELIS, NPL, United Kingdom). A final correction factor was applied to account for the partial volume effect (0.99(3) and 0.89(2) for ^{161}Tb Tb- and ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE, respectively) based on a cross-calibration study in which tumor uptake measured with *in vivo* SPECT and *ex vivo* gamma counter were compared 2 h after injection with ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE (n = 4) or ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE (n = 5).

B.1.3.3 Longitudinal SPECT Imaging

For the longitudinal SPECT study, mice were injected with a low activity (30 MBq; n = 4) and a high activity (90 MBq; n = 3) of 1 nmol ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE, to verify whether the tumor time-activity profile $f(t)$ was consistent among different mice and independent of the injected activity. The kinetics of ^{177}Lu Lu-DOTATATE were assumed to be identical to ^{161}Tb Tb-DOTATATE, based on the findings of a previous *in vitro* study (146). SPECT/CT imaging was performed at 2 h, 1 d, 2 d, 3 d, 6 d, 10 d and 14 d p.i. . The tumor uptake was measured at each time point, normalized to the uptake at 2 h p.i., decay corrected and fitted to a bi-exponential curve

$$f(t) = f_0 \cdot (c \cdot e^{-\lambda_1 \cdot t} + (1 - c) \cdot e^{-\lambda_2 \cdot t}). \quad (\text{B.3})$$

with

$$1/f_0 = c \cdot e^{-\lambda_1 \cdot 2h} + (1 - c) \cdot e^{-\lambda_2 \cdot 2h} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

being the relative tumor uptake at t 2 h p.i. By assuming the tumor uptake to be linear during the first 2 h, equation (B.2) can be calculated as:

$$\tilde{a} = a_{2h} \cdot \int_0^{2h} \frac{t}{2h} dt + a_{2h} \cdot \int_{2h}^{\infty} f_0 \cdot (c \cdot e^{-\lambda_1 \cdot t} + (1 - c) \cdot e^{-\lambda_2 \cdot t}) \cdot e^{-\lambda_p t} dt \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$= a_{2h} \cdot 1h + a_{2h} \cdot f_0 \cdot \left(\frac{c \cdot e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_p)2h}}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_p} + \frac{(1 - c) \cdot e^{-(\lambda_2 + \lambda_p)2h}}{\lambda_2 + \lambda_p} \right) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

B.1.3.4 S-Value Simulations for Tumor Absorbed Dose Calculations

S-values were simulated in GATE for spherical tumors with a homogeneous activity distribution $s_{T,het}$ (147) and a wide range of volumes, ranging from a single cell up to 10 mm^3 . For each tumor, the appropriate S-value was estimated for the corresponding tumor volume using linear interpolation. Meanwhile, the emission spectra for the β^- , IC and Auger electrons that were needed as input for the simulations, were taken from ICRP107 (4).

In addition, subcellular heterogeneity of the activity distribution was taken into account to estimate the tumor absorbed dose, since binding of radiolabeled DOTATATE within the cell is not homogeneous but distributed over the cell membrane (13.6%) and cytoplasm (86.4%). Moreover, the absorbed dose to the cell nucleus

should be evaluated, since this is the most radiosensitive part of the cell (146). To model this heterogeneity within tumor cells, the single cell s-value $s_{C,hom}$, determined by assuming a spherical cell geometry with a homogeneous activity and dose distribution, was subtracted from the tumor s-value $s_{T,hom}$, and replaced by the heterogeneous single cell s-value $s_{C,het}$ to obtain a tumor S-value that considers subcellular heterogeneity:

$$s_{T,het} = s_{T,hom} - s_{C,hom} + s_{C,het} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

The heterogeneous single-cell S-value $s_{C,het}$ was taken from Spoormans *et al.* ($s_{C,het} = 917 \mu\text{Gy Bq}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{cell}^{-1}$ for ^{161}Tb and $s_{C,het} = 243 \mu\text{Gy Bq}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1} \text{cell}^{-1}$ for ^{177}Lu) and multiplied with the cell volume ($V_C = 9.04 \times 10^{-7} \text{mm}^3$), to get the normalized s-value (146). To obtain an estimate for the homogeneous single cell s-value $s_{C,hom}$, the simulated s-value for a spherical tumor with uniform activity distribution was interpolated to the cell volume.

B.1.3.5 Heterogeneous Absorbed Dose Distributions

The tumor-growth-model was corrected for absorbed heterogeneity. This required to determine the absorbed dose distributions within the tumors. Two methodologies were applied, being digital autoradiography and SPECT imaging, for which the details are described below.

B.1.3.5.1 Digital Autoradiography Four tumor bearing mice were injected with 1 nmol (30 MBq) [^{161}Tb]Tb-DOTATATE. The tumors were dissected at 2 h p.i. from which 10 μm thick parallel cryo-sections were made at every $\sim 500 \mu\text{m}$ through the tumors. These cryosections were first imaged with digital autoradiography (BeaQuant, AI4R, France) and afterwards stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E).

The cell nuclei were counted, based on the H&E staining, to construct cell density maps (Biodock, US). The resulting parallel cell density maps were manually co-registered and z-extended to make a 3D-reconstruction. The autoradiography images were decay corrected and normalized to a constant activity concentration per tissue section. The latter normalization was to correct for potential variations in tissue thickness or detector heterogeneity which could affect the absolute count rate. Next, these images were registered to their corresponding cell density maps, and a 3D activity distribution map was reconstructed. This relative activity map was used as input for voxelised dose simulations in GATE as relative activity distribution for both ^{161}Tb and ^{177}Lu (input spectra from ICRP107 (4)). The output was an absorbed dose per voxel, which was combined with the cell density map to get a dose-volume-histogram for the dose per cell. This step reduced the impact of regions with a low absorbed dose due to a low cell density. Finally, this was corrected to the number of simulated decays and tumor volume to get an s-value s_i , that expresses the absorbed dose d_i for a fraction of cells n_i/N per nuclear decay in 1 mm^3 tumor volume. We assumed that the distribution of s-values was independent on the injected activity, since the injected peptide amount remained constant (1 nmol) in the efficacy study that was used for validation of the model. The resulting dose-volume-histograms, normalized to the s-values for a uniform sphere, are shown in figure B.1.

Figure B.1: The dose volume histograms for $n = 4$ CA20948 tumors, 2 h after injection with 1 nmol, 30 MBq [¹⁶¹Tb]Tb-DOTATATE, determined using digital autoradiography and H&E staining. The histograms show the simulated s-values, normalised to the s-values for a uniform spherical tumor, on a logarithmic scale, with on the y-axis the fraction of cells within each bin. Sigma is the Coefficient of Variance(std/mean) for absorbed dose distribution in each tumor.

B.1.3.5.2 SPECT The SPECT images provided the activity distribution for the individual tumors at tissue level (voxel size = 400 μm). These images were used as input for voxelised GATE simulations to determine the corresponding heterogeneous dose-map for the β^- electrons. For the absorbed dose from the IC and Auger electrons, the activity distribution was multiplied with the normalized spherical s-values, since their range was small compared to the voxel size. The total absorbed dose per voxel was then again corrected for subcellular heterogeneity with equation B.7.

B.2 Supplemental Figures

Figure B.2: The tumor uptake at 2 h p.i. (A, B), tumor absorbed dose (C) and tumor doubling time (D) in function of the injected activity for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ and $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$. The tumor uptake is measured from the SPECT images, and expressed in both activity concentration (A) and peptide amount (B) after a correction for the different molar activities.

Figure B.3: The tumor growth curves of all individual mice, per group for $[^{177}\text{Lu}]\text{Lu-DOTATATE}$ (A: 20 Gy, B: 33 Gy, C: 44 Gy, D: 63 Gy, E: 66 Gy), $[^{161}\text{Tb}]\text{Tb-DOTATATE}$ (A: 13 Gy, B: 27 Gy, C: 41 Gy, D: 50 Gy, E: 66 Gy), cold DOTATATE (Vehicle) and saline (control). The markers show the caliper measurements and the curves show the corresponding fit of equation 6.2.

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